

Bio-hybrid robots: Higher plants as control elements of robotic systems.

Author: Michal Seidl,
OpenTechLab Jablonec nad Nisou s. r. o.
IČ: 08111693
B. Němcové 10
Jablonec nad Nisou, Czech Republic

Jablonec nad Nisou, 19. February 2023

Abstract

Bio-hybrid robots represent a new type of robotic system that combines biological elements and machine technology. In this study, I focused on the question of whether plants can be rational users of robotic platforms. I demonstrated that plants have the ability to control a robotic chassis and use it to satisfy their needs. In the paper, I described my approach to researching and implementing a bio-hybrid robot that shows plants as capable of being rational users of this technology. I showed that my method allows plants to take control of the robot and use it to perform tasks in both familiar and unfamiliar environments. The results of my work bring new possibilities in the field of robotic systems and artificial intelligence, and can find application in industries or further research.

The contents:

1. Introduction

- 1.1. Plant electrical activity**
- 1.2. The aim of the work and the ways I intend to achieve it**

2. Theoretical section

- 2.1. Biological and technical aspects of bio-hybrid robots and plant physiology**
- 2.2. The history of research on plant electrical activity**
- 2.3. Origin and propagation of electrical signals in plants**

3. Experimental section

- 3.1. Design and assembly of equipment for measuring plant electrical activity**
 - 3.1.2. Choice of method for measuring plant electrical activity**
 - 3.1.3. Setting up and calibration of the electrophytograph**
 - 3.1.4. Placing electrodes on a plant**
- 3.2. Verification of reactive values of plant signals in response to various stimuli**
 - 3.2.1. Plant experimenter**
 - 3.2.2. The first measurement of plant experimenter's electrical activity**
 - 3.2.3. Comparison and evaluation of the first set of measured signals**
 - 3.2.4. Responses to stimuli in the electrical activity of the plant experimenter**
 - 3.2.5. The relationship between plant electrical activity and external stimuli**
 - 3.2.5.1. Design and implementation of a convolutional neural network for detection and classification of plant electrical activity signals**
 - 3.2.5.2. The collection of classified signals**
 - 3.2.5.3. Design and Implementation of a Convolutional Neural Network for Classification of Action Potentials in Plant Electrical Activity**
- 3.3. Design of models and algorithms for controlling plant motors in various environments**
 - 3.3.1. Model based on natural plant movement**
 - 3.3.2. Model based purely on natural learning abilities of plants**
 - 3.3.3. Model hybrid**

4. The construction of a bio-hybrid robot and experimental verification of the plant's ability to learn to control the robotic platform

- 4.1. The production and assembly of the bio-hybrid robot**
- 4.2. Experimental verification of the ability of a plant to learn to control a robotic platform**
 - 4.2.1. First launch of the bio-hybrid robot**
 - 4.2.1.1. Experiment goals**
 - 4.2.1.2 Methodology for experiment EX_BHR_0_1**
 - 4.2.1.3. Method of plant attachment**
 - 4.2.1.4. The preparation for starting the experiment**
 - 4.2.1.5. The results of the experiments during the first launch of the bio-hybrid robot**
 - 4.2.2. Methodology of teaching a plant to consciously control a robotic platform**

- 4.2.2.1. Design and Description of the Teaching Method
- 4.2.3. Experimental verification of the proposed teaching method
 - 4.2.3.1. First set of epochs
 - 4.2.3.2. Second set of epochs
 - 4.2.3.3. A set of epochs with an increased threshold value of P1415
 - 4.2.3.4. Unexpected observations during the continuous operation of BHR1
- 4.3. Basic verification of the hypothesis of natural adaptability of plants to BHR1
 - 4.3.1. Methodology of the experiment
 - 4.3.2. Execution of Experiment EX_BHR_2
 - 4.3.2.1. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_1
 - 4.3.2.2. Analysis of data related to the phenomenon J_BHR_1
 - 4.3.2.3. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_2
 - 4.3.2.4. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_3
 - 4.3.2.5. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_4
 - 4.3.3. Evaluation of experiment EX_BHR_2
- 4.4. Replication of experiment EX_BHR_2 with a different plant
 - 4.4.1. Optimizing the conditions of the EX_BHR_3 experiment for repeated verification of the hypothesis about the plant's autoadaptation ability to BHR1
 - 4.4.2. Methodology of the experiment EX_BHR_3
 - 4.4.3. Conducting the EX_BHR_3 experiment
 - 4.4.3.1. Comparison of plant stress level development after the first activation of BHR1 and BHR2
 - 4.4.3.2. Verification of the reliability of EFG signal classification by neural network NN2
 - 4.4.3.3. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_1
 - 4.4.3.4. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_2
 - 4.4.3.5. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_3
 - 4.4.3.6. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_4
 - 4.4.3.7. Manifestations of the phenomenon J_BHR_5
 - 4.4.3.7.1. Methodology for testing the phenomenon J_BHR_5 on BHR2
 - 4.4.3.7.2. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_5
 - 4.4.3.8. The event of the change in behavior of frequencies 14 and 15Hz - phenomenon J_BHR_6
- 4.5. Modernization and expansion of the BHR system: Experiments on the interaction between BHR2 and BHR3
 - 4.5.1. Comparison of the development of plant stress levels after the first activation of BHR2 and BHR3
 - 4.5.2. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_4
 - 4.5.3. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_5
 - 4.5.4. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_6
 - 4.5.5. Interactions between BHR2 and BHR3
 - 4.5.5.1. Conditions of the experiment EX_BHR_5
 - 4.5.5.2. Results of experiment EX_BHR_5
- 4.6. Supplementary experiments
 - 4.6.1. Experiment EX_BHR_6
 - 4.6.2. Experimental procedure description
 - 4.6.3. Results of experiment EX_BHR_6

5. Discussion

5.1. Summary of results

5.2. Interpretation of results

5.2.1. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_6

5.2.2. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_2

5.2.3. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_3

5.2.4. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_4

5.2.5. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_5

5.2.6. Interpretation of the mutual relationships of the described phenomena

5.2.6.1. Optimistic approach

5.2.6.2. Skeptic approach

5.2.6.3. Interpretive Conclusion

Sources and references:

- Taiz, L., & Zeiger, E. (2010). *Plant physiology*. Sinauer Associates, Inc. Publishers.
- Hedrich, R., & Lautner, S. (2020). *Electrophysiology of plants*. Springer International Publishing.
- Fromm, J., & Lautner, S. (2007). Electrical signals and their physiological significance in plants. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 30(3), 249-257.
- Gilroy, S., & Trewavas, A. (2010). Signal processing and transduction in plant cells: the end of the beginning?. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology*, 2(5), 389-397.
- Baluška, F. (2006). *Plant neurobiology: From Pavlovian conditioning to memories*. Berlin: Springer.
- Baluška, F., & Mancuso, S. (2013). Plant neurobiology: from sensory biology, via plant communication, to social plant behavior. *Cognitive Processing*, 14(1), 3-19.
- Brenner, E. D., Stahlberg, R., Mancuso, S., Vivanco, J., & Baluška, F. (2006). Plant neurobiology: An integrated view of plant signaling. *Trends in Plant Science*, 11(8), 413-419.
- Vodeneev, V. A., Volkov, A. G., & Carpentier, R. (2019). Biophysics of plant electrophysiology: Signaling and communication at the vegetative level. *Progress in biophysics and molecular biology*, 146, 61-85.
- Volkov, A. G., & Carrell, H. (2007). *Plant electrophysiology: methods and cell electrophysiology*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Stahlberg, R., Cosentino, K., & Trewavas, A. (2002). Electrical signals and their physiological significance in plants. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 25(3), 249-258.
- Fleurat-Lessard, P., & Bonnet, B. (1984). Electrical potential variations in relation to growth and differentiation. In *Plant Growth Substances* (pp. 537-548). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Jaffe, M. J. (1973). Thigmonastic Stimuli in Higher Plants. *Plant Physiology*, 51(1), 1-6.
- Zimmermann, M. R., Maischak, H., Mithöfer, A., Boland, W., & Felle, H. H. (2009). System potentials, a novel electrical long-distance apoplasmic signal in plants, induced by wounding. *Plant Physiology*, 149(3), 1593-1600.
- Vodeneev, V. A., Orlova, L. A., & Drachev, L. A. (2012). The electrical signal in higher plants: mechanisms of generation and propagation. *Russian Journal of Plant Physiology*, 59(3), 283-306.
- "Learning and Memory in Plants" od Mancuso a Baluška, (2017). *Plant Signaling & Behavior*.
- "Intelligence in Plants: Lessons from the Classical Botanical Literature" od Trewavas, (2016), *Plant, Cell & Environment*.
- Vicente Raja, Paula L. Silva, Roghaieh Holghoomi & Paco Calvo - „The dynamics of plant nutation“, (2020), *Nature*.
- Bray, D. Molecular networks: the top-down view. *Science* 301, 1864–1865 (2003)

Introduction

1.1. Plant electrical activity

Unlike animals, plants do not have a specialized nervous system. This means that they do not have specialized nerve cells or brains. Instead, plants have a complex communication system that allows for the transfer of information between different parts of the plant and between neighboring plants.

The basis of this system are so-called phytohormones, which are chemical substances produced in various parts of the plant that transmit information about the surrounding conditions and internal processes in the plant. Phytohormones are transmitted throughout the entire plant via special channels (vessels) and also through interactions between cells.

Another key element of communication in plants are electrical signals, which are produced during various processes in the plant, such as leaf movement, root growth, or in response to external stimuli such as light, temperature, vibrations, sound, or mechanical stimuli. These signals are transmitted throughout the entire plant and can be interpreted as signals about various conditions in the environment.

At the same time, higher plants are characterized by their inability to leave their environment in the face of adverse changes. However, by regulating the expression of genetic information, plants can respond to external stimuli and adapt to new situations to some extent.

Overall, it can be said that even plants have a very complex system of internal and external communication that allows for the transfer of information and response to various stimuli. Although they do not have a nervous system, plants have the ability to perceive and respond to their environment, thus ensuring their survival and successful growth.

1.2. The aim of the work and the ways I intend to achieve it

This work aims to investigate the abilities of plants to utilize robotic systems to fulfill their natural needs while also seeking to design an autonomous bio-hybrid robotic system. This system will include equipment for measuring the electrical activity of plants and neural networks for interaction between the plant and its robotic platform. The goal is to demonstrate that my method enables plants to successfully perform tasks in an unfamiliar environment, which could be useful in industrial, research, or military applications.

2. Theoretical section

2.1. Biological and technical aspects of bio-hybrid robots and plant physiology

In this part of the work, I will focus on the properties of plants that enable their use as control elements in robotic systems. I will also focus on the technical aspects of bio-hybrid robots, particularly on how plants are integrated into robotic systems.

Research in the field of bio-hybrid robots generally involves the use of biological components (bacteria, plants, fungi, animals) to improve the performance of robotic systems. In contrast, in this work, I focused on the use of robotic systems to expand the natural response capabilities of plants,

specifically based on plant physiology.

Plants have the ability to perceive their environment and respond to it through various mechanisms. For example, plant leaves can move in response to light stimuli or when the plant is damaged. Similarly, plant roots can grow towards sources of water or nutrients and circumvent obstacles in the soil.

These properties are advantageous for using plants as control elements in robotic systems. If a plant can perceive its surroundings and respond to them, it can be used to control the movement of a robotic system. For example, a plant can decide when to leave a dangerous place and move to a safer one.

Furthermore, in this part of the work, I will address the technical aspects of bio-hybrid robots, particularly the ways in which plants are integrated into robotic systems. There are several ways to connect plants to robotic systems. One of them is using electrophysical methods, such as electrodes, which allow measuring the electrical activity of plants.

Another option is using chemical stimuli, such as substances contained in plants that can be detected by sensors. For the purposes of research and this work, electrophysical methods will be used to measure the electrical activity of plants.

2.2. The history of research on plant electrical activity

The history of research on the electrical activity of plants dates back to the early 18th century when Italian physicist and physician Luigi Galvani discovered that electrical impulses could influence the muscle contractions of animals. These observations led to the hypothesis that living organisms have electrical activity. Several decades later, this concept was applied to plants. In 1848, German physicist Julius von Sachs discovered that plants produce electrical signals during growth and in response to various stimuli.

In the following decades, numerous experiments were conducted on plants, revealing various forms of electrical activity. For example, in 1968, British physiologist J.C. Salkowski discovered that plants produce weak electrical signals that can be measured and used to diagnose various plant conditions, including stress and disease.

In the 1970s and 1980s, research on the electrical activity of plants focused on studying bioelectrical signals in plant nerve cells and the influence of electrical activity on various physiological processes, such as flower movement. These studies were supported by the development of new technologies, such as microelectrodes and electrophysiological methods.

In recent decades, research on the electrical activity of plants has expanded to include the study of interactions between plants and their environment, including signaling pathways that allow plants to respond to various stimuli, such as light, temperature, and sound. This research also includes the investigation of the use of plant electrical activity in applications such as biotesting, industrial production, and agriculture.

2.3. Origin and propagation of electrical signals in plants

Plants produce electrical signals through ions moving across cell membranes. These ions create an electrical potential between the external and internal environment of the cell. Plants use these

electrical signals to communicate with their surroundings and coordinate their own cellular functions.

One of the most significant electrical signals in plants is called an action potential. This signal is generated when there is a sudden change in external conditions, such as plant injury, predator presence, or changes in light conditions. Action potentials can spread at a speed of several centimeters per second and can propagate throughout the entire plant.

The basis for the spread of the action potential in the plant's body is the ion channels in the cell membranes. In the normal state, these channels are closed and ions cannot freely move between the external and internal environment of the cell. However, when an action potential occurs, the channels open and ions begin to rapidly move between cells. This movement of ions creates an electric current that spreads throughout the plant and generates the action potential.

Action potentials are important for coordinating cellular functions and the plant's response to stressful situations. For example, when a plant is attacked by insects, it generates an action potential that spreads throughout the entire plant and activates defense mechanisms. Research in this field has helped to better understand how plants perceive and respond to their environment, and the mechanisms that enable them to survive in various stressful situations.

3. Experimental section

The research is based on a series of consecutive experiments. In the first part, I focus on constructing suitable apparatus for measuring the electrical activity of plants and evaluating the signals. In the second part, I verify whether the signals obtained by the apparatus contain values that could be considered as responses to various stimuli, such as touch from living and non-living objects, heat, cold, light, noise, and vibrations. In the third part, I conduct a series of experiments in which specific stimuli are presented to the test plants, and then the corresponding patterns are identified in the electrical activity of the plants. The goal of these three parts is to understand the relationships between signals in the electrical activity of plants and external stimuli. Before the fourth part of the experiment, I focus on creating models and algorithms based on the findings from the previous experiments, which will enable plants to perform motor control actions and respond to changes in their environment. In the fourth part of the experiment, I then focus on constructing a robotic platform with wheels, in which the plant will be placed and connected, and verifying whether the plant learns to control the platform. In the fifth part of the experiment, I construct a second identical bio-hybrid robot and evaluate the similarities in the data and observations to determine whether the plants control their platform based on conscious decisions or reflexively or randomly. Finally, I will also investigate the discovered phenomenon of plants' ability to detect and recognize passers-by.

3.1. Design and assembly of equipment for measuring plant electrical activity

3.1.2. Choice of method for measuring plant electrical activity

I have decided to use a non-invasive method for measuring the electrical activity of plants, which involved using contact, dry, non-polarizable Ag/AgCl electrodes placed on the surface of the leaves and roots of the plant. This approach minimizes stress on the plant during measurement and reduces signal distortion caused by plant reactions, including healing.

I attached the electrodes to the plant using special clips, which provided sufficient pressure for the electrodes and prevented direct damage to the plant due to the electrode and clip pressure. This approach allowed me to place the electrodes on the plant for a long time without negative consequences for the plant.

For measuring electrical activity, I used a single-channel DLR electroencephalograph (EEG) Click-EEG from the manufacturer Mikro-e, which was originally designed for measuring electrical activity in the human brain. These EEG modules are simple but very precise and efficient, and I have previously verified their effectiveness in my research on non-invasive connections between the human brain and computer.

Although many measurements of plant electrical activity are performed using instruments originally intended for measuring MYO signals (e.g. ECG), I decided to use an electroencephalograph for its high sensitivity and ability to measure voltage changes in units of microvolts. The EEG module signal is further processed by a microcomputer, which samples the signal at a frequency of 128 Hz and performs real-time spectral analysis of the signal using fast Fourier transform for frequencies 1-30 Hz. The curve of the plant's electrical activity signal and the results of its spectral analysis are then wirelessly transmitted to a PC, where they can be further processed.

I chose low sampling frequencies and monitored frequencies in spectral analysis as suitable for monitoring low-frequency action potentials of plant electrical activity and for reactions to stimuli that plants are exposed to during experiments.

To ensure flawless measurement of plant electrical activity, I solved the power supply of the apparatus with a lithium-ion battery, which eliminates possible signal interference from the power grid. This step also enabled the portability of the apparatus, allowing me to conduct measurements of electrical activity in any plant in the outdoors.

For the purposes of this research, I created the measuring apparatus described above, which I named the electrophytograph (EFG), and I will continue to use this name in the paper.

Image 1 - Basic schematic of the electrophytograph (EFG)

Image 2 - Prototype of the Elektrofytograf Apparatus

3.1.3. Setting up and calibration of the electrophytograph

Please translate: To adjust the signal amplification level of the Click-EEG electroencephalography module precisely, there is a trimmer available that can be used for adjustment. For this purpose, I have a small calibration apparatus available, which was originally assembled for calibrating and verifying the apparatus for non-invasive linking of the human brain and computer in my previous research. This apparatus mainly consists of a signal generator and an oscilloscope and allows for precise adjustment of the signal amplification level by comparing the input and output signal values.

I also used this calibration apparatus to verify the correct setting of the signal sampling frequency and the outputs of the spectral analysis. In this case, I compared the input signal with the outputs processed by the microcomputer to ensure measurement accuracy and signal analysis correctness.

3.1.4. Placing electrodes on a plant

I attached the electrodes to the plants using three different methods so that I could compare the propagation of electrical signals through the plant. Specifically:

A1 - The right electrode was connected to the strongest* leaf on the right side of the plant, the left electrode to the strongest* leaf on the left side, and the DRL electrode to the leaf closest to the roots.

A2 - The right electrode was connected to the strongest* leaf on the right side of the plant, the left electrode to the strongest* leaf on the left side, and the DRL electrode to the surface of the center of the roots.

A3 - The right electrode was attached to the surface of the roots on the right side of the plant, the left electrode to the surface of the roots on the left side, and the DRL electrode to the center of the roots.

**) The strongest leaf refers to the leaf that is dominant in that particular spot, exhibits high vitality, and has negligible damage.*

Initially, experiments were repeated with all three electrode placement methods to compare which method is the most suitable for achieving permanent electrode placement and obtaining the necessary data for controlling the robotic system.

3.2. Verification of reactive values of plant signals in response to various stimuli

3.2.1. Plant experimenter

With regard to the nature of the experiments that will be conducted on the plant, I decided to choose a plant species that is highly resistant to environmental stress, despite the fact that the measuring method is non-invasive. The selection criteria included not only the plant species, but also its age (young plant) and the health of its above-ground and underground parts. The final choice fell on a cutting seedling of *Pelargonium zonale*, which had grown to a height of approximately 15 cm. The experimenter's plant was then transplanted into a new pot with a volume of 0.7 dm³, filled with new fertilized soil for indoor plants. Prior to the start of the experiments, the plant was given seven days to adapt to and acclimate to the new environment.

3.2.2. The first measurement of plant experimenter's electrical activity

Before the first connection of the plant, I performed a 30-minute measurement without connection to the plant at the location of its placement, in order to obtain a reference sample of the parasitic signal. I will later use this sample to identify parasitic values in the signal obtained from the plant. After measuring the parasitic signal, I attached the plant to the EFG apparatus using method A1, as described in section 3.1.4, and performed 30 minutes of continuous measurement of electrical activity without exposing the plant to any further stimuli. This gave me the first record of measured values for the A1 electrode attachment method. I repeated the process for methods A2 and A3, with a 60-minute break between measurements to allow the plant to recover. I compared the obtained records and used them as control records for comparing the signal obtained through all electrode attachment methods.

3.2.3. Comparison and evaluation of the first set of measured signals

The aim of the first series of preliminary measurements (denoted as Data_0) was to verify whether there are self-similar patterns in the signals obtained by all three methods of plant attachment, which are not caused by noise or parasitic signal. Since no targeted stimuli were induced in the plant during the acquisition of the initial signal recordings, it was not possible to evaluate the signal propagation through the plant. After comparing the data, I found that there is a significant difference between the signal obtained by the blank measurement and the signals obtained using all three methods of plant attachment. This difference is recorded in graphs 1 and 2:

Graph 1 - Representative sample of spectral analysis of the signal obtained by measuring without connection to the plant. The x-axis shows the order of measurements, the y-axis shows the amplitude values of frequencies from 1 Hz to 30 Hz, and the color coding is shown in the legend.

Graph 2 - Representative sample of spectral analysis of the signal obtained by measuring the electrical activity of the plant connected using method A2. The x-axis shows the order of measurement, while the y-axis shows the amplitude values of frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 30 Hz. The color coding is explained in the legend.

Due to the lack of detailed knowledge for further analysis, it was not possible to distinguish the signal of the plant's electrical activity using each individual connection method with the naked eye. Therefore, I present only a representative sample obtained using one of the methods - method A2.

From the measurement results on the EFG without plant connection, a relatively high level of noise can be observed, which could affect further experiments. To diagnose the origin of the noise, I performed measurements on the equipment and found that the biggest contribution to the noise occurs at the interface between the EEG module and the ADC input of the microcontroller.

To reduce the noise, I added a ceramic capacitor with a capacity of 100 nF between GND and the ADC input of the microcontroller. The difference in the noise level of the data obtained from the EFG before and after adding the capacitor is presented in graphs 3 and 4:

Graph 3 - Representative sample of spectral analysis of the signal obtained from measuring without connecting to the plant and without adding a capacitor. The x-axis represents the order of measurement, and the y-axis represents the amplitude values of frequencies from 1 Hz to 30 Hz. The color resolution is indicated in the legend.

Graph 4 - A representative sample of spectral analysis of a signal obtained by measuring without connection to a plant with an installed noise filter - capacitor. The x-axis represents the order of measurement, and the y-axis represents the amplitude values of frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 30 Hz. The color resolution is indicated in the legend.

By comparing the data outputs, it is evident that the addition of a simple noise filter led to a reduction in the noise level by more than 85%.

3.2.4. Responses to stimuli in the electrical activity of the plant experimenter

The aim of this set of experimental measurements (Data_1) was to determine whether action potentials in response to stimuli appear in the data of the plant's electrical activity and to determine how these potentials propagate through the plant's body. For this purpose, precise timing control of the repetitions of each experiment was necessary for all methods of connecting the plant to the EFG.

For the first set of measurements (Data_1_1), the plant was exposed to two consecutive stimuli with a time interval of 30 s - the passage of a person around the plant at a distance of 0.5 m (p2) and noise caused by clapping hands at a distance of 1 m (p1).

The stimulus of a person passing by the plant was included in the experiment because during testing, I noticed a significant reaction in the plant's electrical activity to this stimulus. This fact caught my attention, and I believe that plants' ability to perceive people passing by has the potential for many practical applications. As part of my research, I will therefore focus on this interesting question separately.

Both stimuli resulted in well-visible action potentials in the plant's electrical activity, which are marked in figure 3:

Figure 3 – Record of the measurement of the electrical activity of the Pelargonium zonale plant with marked action potentials p1 and p2. The A2 method of connecting the plant was used. The potential p1 is a response to noise, and the potential p2 is a response to the passage of a person.

According to Figure 3, the action potentials in the electrical activity of the Pelargonium zonale plant are clearly visible to the naked eye. It is evident that both types of action potentials differ from each other and have a different manifestation in electrical activity. Repeated experiments with connection methods A1 and A3 showed that the manifestation of action potentials in response to a particular stimulus is consistent, meaning it is possible to distinguish action potentials induced by different stimuli.

From the Data_1_1 measurement set, it cannot be determined with absolute certainty how the action potential propagates through the plant's body. This finding is clearly due to a lack of data for evaluation. Nevertheless, it was possible to preliminarily state that both types of action potentials

propagate from the aboveground part of the plant towards the underground part of the plant, and their manifestation in spectral analysis data is very similar, regardless of the chosen method of connecting the plant.

An interesting phenomenon of minimal change in activity in the frequency range of 14 and 15 Hz was observed from the collected data. No change in activity or action potential was observed at these frequencies. The signal amplitude at these frequencies remained approximately constant throughout the measurement with maximum deviations of up to 0.3%, likely caused by noise. This finding is important and will be further investigated in the next phases of research.

The second set of measurements (marked Data_1_2) focused on the plant's electrical activity in response to stimuli from living and non-living objects. The goal was to determine whether the plant reacted differently to these two types of stimuli and whether the difference between them was easily distinguishable.

To elicit the stimulus from a living object, I used the fingers of my right hand, and for the stimulus from a non-living object, I used a wooden rod with a diameter of 8 mm and a length of 200 mm.

To minimize the influence of any electric charge from the contacting objects on the measured electrical activity of the plant, the contact point is used as far away from the electrodes as possible in terms of the plant's body path. This ensures the longest path for transferring the electric charge from the object to the electrode, and therefore the highest natural resistance (measured resistance on the poured plant *Pelargonium zonale* is 94.35 k Ω on a 10 mm stem with a diameter of 3 mm, and the measured capacity is 38 pF on a 10 mm stem with a diameter of 3 mm).

The contact point was chosen so that the shortest path was 92 mm long and led to electrode DRL. The minimum measured resistance on this path was 838.72 k Ω , which corresponded to the calculation. I also measured the minimum capacity of the path at 102 μ F, which also corresponded to the theoretical assumption.

From the measured parameters, it follows that the plant in this path can absorb a relatively large capacity of electric charge and at the same time offer strong resistance to the conducted electric current. However, the touching objects were grounded within the experiment. Experiment Data_1_2 was performed only with the plant connected using method A2.

For both touches, well-visible action potentials repeatedly appeared in the plant's electrical activity, which are marked in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Record of the measurement of the electrical activity of the *Pelargonium zonale* plant with marked action potentials p3 and p4. Method of plant attachment A2 was used. Potential p3 is a response to touch by a living object, potential p4 is a response to touch by a non-living object.

Because the aim of the Data_1 experiment set was to determine whether action potentials in response to stimuli appear in the electrical activity data of the connected plant, and how these potentials propagate throughout the plant body, I consider the outputs from the experiments sufficient to draw conclusions and move on to further stages of research. For all stimuli applied, the electrical activity shows clear responses expressed by significant amplitude changes at specific frequencies. These responses are easily distinguishable from each other and manifest as parallel excitation across frequencies. The signal propagates throughout the entire plant, and the measurement quality, or the ability to detect action potentials, is not significantly affected by electrode placement, as the EFG apparatus is sensitive enough to capture even slight changes in the signal within the dimensions of the experimenter's plant.

3.2.5. The relationship between plant electrical activity and external stimuli

3.2.5.1. Design and implementation of a convolutional neural network for detection and classification of plant electrical activity signals

For signal detection and classification, I designed and implemented a simple convolutional neural network in the JAVA programming language, which is capable of detecting and classifying the signal of plant electrical activity. Convolutional neural networks have been mainly used in recent years for processing image and sound data, but due to their ability to detect and classify complex

patterns, they are increasingly used in the field of time signal processing. The architecture of the designed network consists of 30 neurons in the input layer, two hidden layers of 18 neurons each, and an output layer with four neurons. The input layer of the network is connected to the pre-processed signal of plant electrical activity - spectral analysis data, which is further processed using convolutional and max-pooling layers of the hidden layers. The output of the network consists of four neurons, each corresponding to one class of signals: silence, noise, action potential, and signal mixing. This neural network enables automatic and objective classification of plant electrical activity signals, which significantly facilitates the analysis of measured data. Thanks to online learning, the network can be trained and optimized during experiments, which allows for quick response to changes in data and improvement of network performance.

I have left a convolutional neural network permanently connected to receive real-time data from the experimenter's plant through the EFG method A2 (Data_2_1) for a period of seven days. During this time, the neural network completed 423,360 epochs, which is the number of times it passed through the entire training dataset (approximately one epoch every 700ms).

The outputs from the network now reliably represent the probabilities that a given input signal belongs to each of the four signal classes - silence, noise, action potential, or signal interference. These probabilities are computed based on the analysis and processing of the signal input to the network, which is preprocessed and further processed in the convolutional and max-pooling layers of the hidden layers.

If the input signal is silent, the output neuron for silence has the highest probability, while the probabilities of the remaining classes are low. Similarly, if the input signal is noise, the output neuron for noise has the highest probability, while the probabilities of the remaining classes are low. If the input signal consists of an action potential, the output neuron for the action potential has the highest probability, while the probabilities of the remaining classes are low. If the input signal is a combination of silence, noise, and action potential, the probabilities for all classes differ significantly depending on the composition of the input signal.

I verified the correct classification of the neural network by gradually presenting data containing previously identified action potentials, silence, and noise. The network was able to correctly classify all presented data. Furthermore, I added up the amplitudes of action potentials and noise in different data samples and repeatedly presented them to the network. The network successfully classified this data as well. Therefore, I consider the network classification to be successful and the classifier usable for further experiments. I named the classifier NN1 for identification purposes.

3.2.5.2. The collection of classified signals

The goal of the experimental measurement set (labeled as Data_2_2) was to obtain a large amount of data on the electrical activity of the plant and categorize it based on action potentials that were elicited by predetermined stimuli. These data will subsequently serve as training and validation data for the convolutional neural network NN2. I included the following stimuli:

P1 - passage of a person near the plant;

P2 - response to touch by a living object;

P3 - response to touch by a non-living object;

P4 - response to a stressful stimulus causing physical damage.

The stimulus P1 was presented to the plant in the following way. The plant was placed in the center of the laboratory on the ground, with only free space within 1 meter of its radius. I placed a paper tape on the ground, 50 cm away from the axis of the flowerpot, as a dotted circle with the center being the flowerpot, to precisely mark the path where a person would walk around the plant. The EFG apparatus was placed on the opposite side of the walking path to minimize the change in its electromagnetic field caused by a person passing by.

Data collection for stimulus P1 was performed by waiting at least 2 meters away from the plant until its electrical activity became calm and stable. Then, I started the data transmission to the NN1 network and walked calmly around the plant on the predetermined path. After 5 seconds, I stopped the data transmission. Data classified by the NN1 network as action potentials were saved in the corresponding folder. I repeated this process a total of 25 times in this experimental set.

Graph 5 - Representative sample of data from spectral analysis of the signal obtained by measurement and categorization with NN1 for stimuli P1. The x-axis represents the order of measurement, and the y-axis represents the amplitude values of frequencies from 1 Hz to 30 Hz, with color coding as indicated in the legend.

frekvence Hz	Sada 1	Sada 2	Sada 3	Sada 4	Sada 5
1	33,85	79,69	88,57	49,52	59,69
2	6,61	67,72	85,42	19,38	63,06
3	159,5	99,17	207,19	37,17	112,36
4	52,95	8,17	149,7	49,56	215,37
5	73,08	91,25	410,9	174,65	61,16
6	568,72	419,69	367,26	209,44	620,06
7	784,62	995,28	939,45	577,94	973,8
8	395,35	501,3	457,25	850,94	800,2
9	300,43	205,48	493,57	239,25	66,06
10	165,41	129,63	245,9	552,69	546,37
11	190,7	416,91	364,19	344,7	283,23
12	56,05	563,29	413,27	113,66	169,21
13	756,7	746,62	798,47	757,77	761,14
14	274,04	280,47	292,96	275,42	289,47
15	179,59	189,79	195,7	188	194,39
16	125,27	155,38	195,06	172,13	146,03
17	223,49	546,33	336,38	435,1	305,53
18	99,28	263,74	144,96	298,16	428,55
19	183,7	299,07	445,94	353,33	302,88
20	300,53	829,52	458,27	640,03	790,85
21	592,43	266,43	237,31	211,25	228,11
22	179,22	199,6	181,26	151,54	156,13
23	120,83	74,92	344,3	124,74	311,44
24	41,9	97,71	313,38	202,83	209,07
25	105,54	252,88	153,57	232,31	162,51
26	144,42	306,04	442,62	146,42	95,39
27	581,47	287,3	265,83	418,48	158,6
28	288,71	225,3	104,08	616,36	128,57
29	277,79	223,3	125,14	735,28	140,39

Table 1 - Values for Graph 5 - A representative sample of spectral analysis data of the signal obtained by measuring and categorizing with NN1 for stimuli P1. Values are expressed as tenths of a percent.

The plant in stimulus P2 was exposed in the following manner. The plant was placed on the ground in the middle of the laboratory so that there was only free space within a radius of 1 m around it. The living object remained stationary in one place during data collection, marked with a label at a distance of 50 cm from the center of the flowerpot. The reason for this was to prevent the occurrence of action potentials caused by a person approaching. To evoke the stimulus of touch with a living object, I used the fingers of my right hand. I placed the EFG apparatus on the opposite side of the location where the living object was located.

The contact point was chosen so that the shortest path was 92 mm long and led to the electrode DRL. The touching object was grounded within the experiment. The same conditions were established as for obtaining the Data_1_2 set.

Data collection for stimulus P2 was carried out by waiting at the label until the plant's electrical activity calmed down and stabilized. Subsequently, I turned on the data transmission to the NN1 network and touched the plant at the designated contact point for approximately 1 second. Then, I waited for an additional 5 seconds and stopped the data transmission. The data classified by the NN1 network as action potentials were again stored in the corresponding folder. I repeated this

process a total of 25 times in this set of experiments.

Graph 6 - Sample data of spectral analysis of the signal obtained by measurement and categorization with the NN1 network for stimuli P2. The x-axis shows the order of measurements, the y-axis shows the amplitude values of frequencies from 1 Hz to 30 Hz, and the color coding is shown in the legend.

frekvence Hz	Sada 1	Sada 2	Sada 3	Sada 4	Sada 5
1	110,16	405,56	538,64	530,44	515,87
2	162,81	162,81	31,1	88,39	112,25
3	201,15	201,15	127,58	292,8	93,26
4	441,46	441,46	715,36	610,88	757,99
5	868,13	868,13	109,02	938,53	689,63
6	295,79	295,79	440,71	315,79	161,24
7	126,9	126,9	200,71	276,9	73,28
8	197,31	197,31	34,23	142,03	323,59
9	578,21	357,7	217,44	193,5	161,46
10	955,96	917,98	100,1	759,93	101,76
11	736,33	689,87	557,71	406,12	674,09
12	230,57	186,22	86,44	246,14	43,27
13	835,41	373,71	529,69	665,33	482,12
14	171,91	170,7	171,34	172,56	171,34
15	291,01	290,9	295,13	296,22	293,14
16	920,93	942,45	951,62	957,96	940,91
17	287,7	128,87	373,8	358,97	136,12
18	199,75	401,26	296,96	232,97	45,36
19	797,91	138,52	114,84	959,61	109,53
20	104,9	152,78	120,8	780,21	980,87
21	191,19	304,79	440,61	193,85	269,26
22	139,7	67,82	95,04	235,73	253,2
23	43,81	334,11	275,33	122,06	220,05
24	491,35	929,18	693,93	727,92	459,61
25	266,16	101,19	106,15	800,86	369,67
26	149,08	334,04	417,99	322,56	311,39
27	202,98	364,63	273,58	155,14	213,82
28	485,31	97,02	625,97	489,19	555,54
29	448,9	410,12	443,59	459,24	454,79

Table 2 - Values for graph 6 - sample data of spectral analysis of the signal obtained by measuring and categorizing with NN1 network for stimuli P2. Values are expressed in tenths of a percent.

For stimulus P3, the plant was exposed in the same way as in the case of stimulus P2, with the difference that a wooden stick with a diameter of 8 mm and a length of 200 mm, identical to that used for obtaining Data_1_2 set, was used to elicit the stimulus by a non-living object.

Data collection for stimulus P3 was performed by waiting at the marker until the electrical activity of the plant calmed down and stabilized. Then, I turned on the data transfer to NN1 network and touched the plant with the wooden stick at the designated contact point for approximately 1 second. After that, I waited for an additional 5 seconds and terminated the data transfer. The data classified as action potentials by the NN1 network were saved in the corresponding folder. I repeated this process a total of 25 times for this set of experiments.

Graph 7 - Sample of spectral analysis data for the signal obtained by measurement and categorization with NN1 networks for stimuli P3. The x-axis shows the measurement sequence, while the y-axis represents the amplitude values of frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 30 Hz. The color coding is shown in the legend.

frekvence Hz	Sada 1	Sada 2	Sada 3	Sada 4	Sada 5
1	295,31	178,07	629,53	189,59	224,9
2	93,84	370,01	370,01	357,81	416,34
3	96,92	930,84	873,01	136,87	116,02
4	712,31	190,39	133,23	679,68	190,38
5	635,3	288,51	132,12	921,1	395,55
6	86,39	332,66	635,96	822,25	713,82
7	175,38	238,19	594,47	916,9	992,85
8	359,03	296,3	144,19	176,38	181,62
9	327,95	544,89	183,39	304,88	667,54
10	513,32	566,5	126,88	190,44	109,9
11	462,7	447,23	940,49	219,59	313,06
12	126,26	342,33	580,76	289,13	239,91
13	682,31	552,05	378,24	808,39	124,99
14	170,52	457,03	559,39	111,29	798,28
15	292,79	763,82	273,2	993,41	107,89
16	948,69	896,81	816,17	120,29	891,48
17	106,59	193,18	528,83	733,28	309,16
18	345,72	341,8	234,06	433,8	368,6
19	119,21	461,62	215,37	517,46	136,21
20	145,24	392,22	228,69	256,21	167,81
21	349,03	195,9	197,24	238,91	160,63
22	216,63	688,24	143,38	293,24	154,37
23	231,54	243,29	815,11	261,2	654,79
24	832,81	316	499,98	700,6	111,86
25	218,07	210,85	703,87	179,1	739,44
26	228,24	348,7	105,62	311,68	113,9
27	49,42	214,04	165,28	116,54	908,96
28	319,51	295,2	206,04	134,58	130,6
29	466,25	690,7	221,49	214,93	479,72

Table 3 - values for graph 7 - a sample of spectral analysis data of the signal obtained by measurement and categorization using the NN1 network for stimuli P3. The values are expressed as tenths of a percent.

In this set of experiments, stimulus P4 was presented to the plant last to prevent the remaining experiments from being disrupted due to induced stress. Stimulus P4 consists of three specific stimuli. The first stimulus (P4_1) involves rough touches from a living object, which do not have the primary goal of causing physical damage, but it may occur. The second stimulus (P4_2) involves physical damage to the leaves, mimicking animal browsing. The third stimulus (P4_3) involves exposing the plant to fire to cause local damage.

The plant was placed on the ground in the middle of the laboratory, so that there was only free space within a radius of 1 meter around it. To create stimuli for the plant, I remained in a fixed position marked by a label at a distance of 50 cm from the center of the pot for the entire data collection period to prevent action potentials caused by changes in my position.

The data collection for stimulus P4 proceeded as follows: First, I waited for the plant to calm down and its electrical activity to stabilize at the marker. Then, I turned on the data transfer to the NN1 network and applied the P4_1 stimulus to the plant using both hands for 1 second. After another 5 seconds, I stopped the data transfer and saved the data identified by the network as action potentials into the appropriate folder. I repeated the whole process 8 times, with 20-minute breaks for plant regeneration. I chose this interval based on observations of the plant's electrical activity, which took about 15 minutes to stabilize after the first measurement.

For the P4_2 stimulus, I followed the same procedure as for P4_1. To simulate animal nibbling, I used my fingertips and nails. I left a 40-minute gap between experiment repetitions, as it took 38 minutes for the plant to stabilize again after the first measurement. I repeated this process 8 times.

Data collection for stimulus P4_3 took place after a three-day break from the P4_2 set. The measurement procedure was as follows: First, I waited for the plant's electrical activity to stabilize at the marker. Then, I turned on the data transfer to NN1 and began exposing the plant to a flame using a gas burner. I directed the flame parallel to the plant's leaves at a distance of 1-2 cm and oscillated the edges of the leaves with the flame three times per second. After that, I waited for 5 seconds and stopped the data transfer. I repeated the measurement three more times with a 24-hour gap between each repetition, as a higher number of repetitions could cause significant damage to the plant's health.

Graph 8 - a sample of spectral analysis data of the signal obtained by measuring and categorizing with NN1 networks for stimuli P4. The x-axis represents the order of the measurements, while the y-axis represents the amplitude values of frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 30 Hz. The color coding is explained in the legend.

frekvence Hz	Sada 1	Sada 2	Sada 3	Sada 4	Sada 5
1	790,78	582,77	362,72	362,35	786,65
2	450,71	437,33	333,41	176,51	186,34
3	385,41	446,8	388,44	598,46	461,08
4	664,2	80,68	136,92	881,22	434,14
5	907,35	411,98	667,61	309,43	121,5
6	170,6	680,1	601,38	251,77	185,44
7	298,12	246,46	352,87	515,31	409,83
8	181,63	354,68	257,11	113,01	208,79
9	939,83	957,81	288,15	831,96	360,74
10	130,6	558,11	592,28	305,25	538,26
11	831,11	513,86	897	466,46	979,72
12	791,09	501,63	375,83	611,42	247,91
13	902,66	761,71	881,46	191,55	104,94
14	308,89	308,89	349,34	366,72	360,03
15	207,6	258,31	235,31	130,78	227,11
16	219,17	267,66	239,85	443,95	107,77
17	116,43	219,08	746,02	344,23	767,02
18	379,45	210,79	534,56	484,49	103,9
19	64,73	135,44	263,54	936,77	340,6
20	172,82	276,08	199,35	119,38	955,12
21	259,83	636,32	637,04	167,05	624,07
22	493,03	273,62	406,22	561,94	517,7
23	134,75	336,73	388,61	437,71	320,84
24	558,99	378,87	317,97	124,05	707,47
25	773,53	144,81	279,52	212,75	554,13
26	345,66	345,66	300,96	515,9	379,57
27	527,47	527,47	370,16	288,75	248,03
28	173,25	474,2	196,35	756,69	410,83
29	139,13	980,31	175,72	608,76	608,1

Table 4 - values for graph 8 - a sample of spectral analysis data of the signal obtained by

measurement and categorization with network NN1 for stimuli P4. The values are expressed in tenths of a percent.

I verified the correct categorization of the data obtained from this set of experiments into the category of action potentials by manually presenting the categorized data again to the NN1 classification network and comparing it with the current outputs.

3.2.5.3. Design and Implementation of a Convolutional Neural Network for Classification of Action Potentials in Plant Electrical Activity

To classify signals of plant electrical activity into categories P1 to P4, I designed and implemented a second simple convolutional neural network in the Java language, which is capable of classifying the plant electrical activity signal into the following categories:

K1 - wandering;

K2 - contact_live;

K3 - contact_non-living;

K4 - stress.

The proposed architecture of the network is similar to the architecture of NN1 because it proved to be effective. However, the training method of the network has been modified, and the number of hidden layers has been reduced to one with 23 neurons. The output of the network again consists of four neurons, each corresponding to one of the categories of signals K1 to K4.

The modifications to the architecture were made to enable training of the network with a smaller amount of data. Thanks to this convolutional neural network NN2, automatic and objective categorization of plant electrical activity signals is possible, which significantly facilitates the analysis and further use of the measured data.

The convolutional neural network NN2 learned to categorize training and validation data after completing 2464 epochs with an error of 0.004. I also verified whether the NN2 network was properly trained on validation data obtained by repeating the Data_2_2 experiment set in a limited manner.

The outputs from the NN2 network reliably represent the probabilities with which the given input signal belongs to each of the four signal categories K1 to K4. These probabilities are calculated based on the analysis and processing of the signal input to the network, which is preprocessed and further processed in the convolutional and max-pooling layers of the hidden layer.

3.3. Design of models and algorithms for controlling plant motors in various environments

For the design of an algorithm for processing the electrical activity signals of plants to control the motors of a robotic platform, I was partially inspired by my research on BCI interfaces - the connection between the human brain and computers for robot control. Thanks to this, I had a relatively complex idea of the technical solution for the robotic platform that would be connected to the plant, and I could adapt models and algorithms to it from the beginning.

The fundamental criterion for designing the control model was established - the movement of the

robotic platform must be an expression of the plant's free will. This means that the plant is not just an integrated sensor for the platform but rather a free user who controls it at will. Designing a model that would meet this basic requirement proved to be a challenging task. Plants are not equipped to perform tasks such as moving to another location, and they have never encountered a change of location caused by their own will throughout history. Thus, it was difficult to determine the starting points on which the model could be built.

The way this research has been approached so far naturally led to the idea that it would be possible to use the NN2 classifier with a predetermined probability threshold to detect stress that would trigger the movement of the robot. However, such a model would inadequately meet the basic requirement of the plant's free will, as the plant would only serve as a sensor in that case. Designing a model to apply the plant's free will in decision-making requires incorporating the plant's ability to demonstrate a certain level of intelligence and learning ability.

In the work "Learning and Memory in Plants" by F. Baluška and colleagues, it is stated that "higher plants actively retain information about past experiences, creating an information background that allows for comparing and evaluating new experiences and responding to them more quickly and effectively in the future." The ability of plants to learn is confirmed by other research, and therefore, it should be possible to create a suitable model for further study.

3.3.1. Model based on natural plant movement

Although plants do not leave their habitats, it does not mean that they are immobile. There are various natural movements that plants perform, such as heliotropic movements (when the plant turns towards the sun), trapping movements (when carnivorous plants catch insects), haptotropic movements (when the plant responds to touch), and thigmotropic movements (when the plant adapts to the external environment, such as solid objects, wind or rain). According to literature, the *Pelargonium zonale*, which is used as a test plant, is capable of performing very slow heliotropic and thigmotropic movements. However, it has not been studied to what extent these movements are reflexive and to what extent the plant is able to decide on them. The fundamental challenge for a model based on natural plant movements is the fact that these movements are not activated and controlled by electrical activity, but through phytohormones and biochemical processes. Therefore, it is essential to first determine whether and how these biochemical processes are connected to plant electrical signals, and whether it is possible to identify these signals retrospectively with specific biochemical activities. Given this challenge, I have decided to keep the model based on plant movements in reserve, if I do not find a more suitable model.

3.3.2. Model based purely on natural learning abilities of plants

Another variant is a model based entirely on the learning abilities of plants. The learning and memory processes described by F. Baluška et al. in their 2017 work "Learning and Memory in Plants" are based on very complex and symbiotic mechanisms, especially in the root system and its extensions. However, these learning processes are very specialized and cannot be generalized due to the complexity of the learning process. Such a model requires the establishment of specific goals, the ability to quantify errors, and feedback for the learning process. However, for plants, this is problematic again, as they have different reaction mechanisms and a different spectrum of stimuli and responses. Therefore, it is not easy to apply models that are used for learning animals

with a central nervous system. Considerations of this model led me to the idea of using changes in the amplitudes of the inactive frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz to control the robot's motors, thus teaching the plant to control movement by making targeted changes in the amplitudes of these two frequencies. The critical challenge for this model remains to create a comprehensive learning method that includes setting goals, quantifying errors, and the feedback process. Given this challenge, I have decided to keep this model in reserve unless I find a more suitable alternative.

3.3.3. Model hybrid

In the end, it proved to be a promising model that combines natural plant learning and classification of plant electrical activity signals using a modified NN2 neural network for signal classification according to different levels of stress and passage of a person around the plant (according to the Data_2_2 dataset).

In this model, motor control is based on monitoring deviations of frequencies 14 and 15 Hz from the set threshold, with the modified NN2 neural network serving as the teacher. The detection of threshold probability of some of the classified categories of plant electrical activity signals results in the connection of motors to the power supply, allowing the plant to physically trigger the motors based on changes in amplitude on the monitored frequencies. In this model, plant learning is thus achieved through the accumulation of experience.

However, this model carries a significant risk in the form of the need to meet several assumptions, such as sufficient intelligence of the plant to understand the situation and perceive escape from danger as a positive reaction. However, it is impossible to determine in advance whether these conditions will be met. Nevertheless, some observations I obtained during experiments suggest that higher plants have a more pronounced intellectual potential than is commonly assumed. For example, it appears that a plant can recognize different people based on their voice, as evidenced by differences in the plant's electrical activity when listening to my voice versus another person's voice. These observed deviations were most pronounced shortly after I applied stress factors to the plant and persisted for up to 3 weeks. Simply put, it seems that the plant remembers its stressor and can distinguish it from other animals of the same species. However, these observations have not been systematically analyzed and verified, so I cannot say with certainty whether my conclusion is true.

Image 5 - A simplified diagram of the model used to build a bio-hybrid robot.

4. The construction of a bio-hybrid robot and experimental verification of the plant's ability to learn to control the robotic platform

Only basic requirements have been set for the robotic platform that will be connected to the plant. Specifically, it must be able to move smoothly forward, backward, right, and left on command, as well as autonomously avoid solid obstacles. Thanks to these minimum requirements, the construction of the platform will be extremely simple. The only special requirements will relate to the appropriate integration of the EFG apparatus and the plant pot.

Given that the EFG apparatus contains a microcomputer with sufficient computing power and the ability to control the robot's actuators (motors), I have decided to integrate motor control directly into the apparatus firmware. As a result, the robotic platform is very simple, consisting only of two continuous servo drives and two infrared sensors for obstacle detection.

4.1. The production and assembly of the bio-hybrid robot

The design of the platform was created using additive manufacturing technology, which allows for the direct printing of solid parts in the laboratory. The emphasis was placed on practical and functional aspects during the design process, while aesthetics were not the primary factor. Requirements for stability and durability were taken into account, so that the platform could withstand the conditions in the vicinity of the plants. At the same time, care was taken to ensure that the construction was as simple as possible and easy to assemble. In addition, compatibility with the EFG apparatus and flowerpot requirements were also taken into consideration.

*Obrázek 6
Testování modelu a algoritmů s upravenou EFG
aparaturou na prototypovacím robotickém podvozku.*

*Obrázek 7
Testování modelu a algoritmů s upravenou EFG
aparaturou na rozpracované platformě v1.*

*Obrázek 8
Zhotovená robotická platforma v1 před implementací
rostliny.*

During the construction of the hardware part of the robotic platform, no unexpected difficulties arose. I solved the power supply of the platform and EFG apparatus with two 18650 Li-ion cells with a total capacity of 5200 mAh. This is sufficient energy capacity for at least four hours of continuous operation. At this stage of the research, I am not considering the possibility of automatic charging, the charging will be done manually.

I integrated the firmware for controlling the robot into the EPG firmware, and I wrote the program in Wiring language in combination with C++.

However, I struggled significantly with determining the threshold value for comparing changes in the monitored frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz. Even careful determination of this threshold value as a fixed percentage of the current level did not yield the desired results because it did not take into account the specific way in which the plant utilizes these frequencies.

I attempted to find an optimal procedure for determining the threshold level and its automatic adaptation depending on the current situation of the bio-hybrid robot.

In the end, I chose an algorithm for determining a suitable threshold value, which periodically monitors the mean amplitude of the entire signal spectrum (1-30 Hz) during its run, as well as the

mean amplitude of the monitored frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz. The threshold for detecting changes in these frequencies is then calculated as the ratio of the mean value of the monitored frequencies to the mean value of the entire spectrum amplitude. This solution has proven to be effective and allows for continuous automatic adjustment of the threshold value depending on the current situation in which the bio-hybrid robot is located. The threshold value is labeled as P1415.

Therefore, the robotic platform was assembled, as seen in Figure 8. It consists of the following three basic parts:

1. The EFG apparatus, which was modified for controlling the motors on the platform and is removable.
2. The chassis with two motors and two infrared proximity sensors.
3. The flowerpot with partitions and integrated connectors for root electrodes.

Each part of the platform was carefully designed and created to complement each other and create an effective and functional whole with the plant. One of the goals was to verify which method of attaching the plant (A1, A2, A3) is most suitable for the bio-hybrid robot. Therefore, the flowerpot was designed with two partitions, creating three separate compartments for specific root parts and electrode connections (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Indication of the division of the root system, placement of individual parts into compartments and display of electrode connection points.

Thanks to this design of the flowerpot, it is easy to switch between the methods of connecting and measuring the electrical activity of the plant, and to implement all three connection methods - A1, A2, and A3.

4.2. Experimental verification of the ability of a plant to learn to control a robotic platform

4.2.1. First launch of the bio-hybrid robot

4.2.1.1. Experiment goals

I consider the first launch to be the zeroth experiment of the epoch. Approximately 60 minutes before the first robot launch, extraordinary biological circumstances occurred. Transplanting a plant, especially interfering with the root ball, is very stressful for it and even life-threatening. Therefore, before starting, I carefully considered how these circumstances could affect the course of the experiment or whether they could be used within the experiment.

Although the first robot start is essentially an uncontrolled experiment, it can also be used to verify the modified classification of plant electrical activity signals using NN2.

Furthermore, I decided to monitor the development of the plant's stress level until it drops below a probability level of 25%. The acquired data will be used to extrapolate the plant's adaptation to the new situation over time and to assess the degree of recovery after invasive interference with the root system (EX_BHR_0_1).

Throughout the duration of the EX_BHR_0_1 experiment, I plan to observe and gather information about the actions and reactions of the bio-hybrid robot in order to make better decisions about the content of the first series of experiments (EX_BHR_0_2).

4.2.1.2 Methodology for experiment EX_BHR_0_1

To ensure consistent data on the plant stress development, I have chosen the following methodology. The plant stress level, determined by the NN2 network, will be recorded in a table every 10 minutes from the first activation until the stress level drops below the 25% probability level. In case the battery runs out, the measurement will be interrupted during battery charging. If the experiment lasts for more than one day, there will be a break between measurements overnight.

To maximize the validity of the plant stress data, the likelihood of stressor recognition and passerby interference will be taken into account. Therefore, the experiment will take place in a closed laboratory with a controlled environment, and disruption of the plant's personal space (a circle with a radius of 1 meter) will only be permitted in extreme cases. The occurrence of such situations will be recorded in the data.

4.2.1.3. Method of plant attachment

For the first launch of the bio-hybrid robot, I chose the method of electrode connection A3, i.e. to the roots of the plant, in order to verify the quality of the signal and the influence of the design of the flowerpot and connection points on it.

4.2.1.4. The preparation for starting the experiment

I calibrated the modified electrophytograph using the already proven method described in Chapter

3.1.3 before connecting the plant. I prepared monitoring software specifically for this purpose, which I wrote in Java. I also verified that the wireless data transmission is functioning correctly and checked the battery level. For the purpose of recording the experiment, I prepared a camera. After completing these preparations, I closed the laboratory and placed the bio-hybrid robot in the same location in the laboratory where the previous experiments Data_1 and Data_2 were conducted.

4.2.1.5. The results of the experiments during the first launch of the bio-hybrid robot

Based on the observed output data from the modified NN2 network, I can confirm that the signal classification is being performed in accordance with previous results and therefore, I can consider it verified.

In experiment EX_BHR_0_1, I monitored the development of the plant stress level over time from the first run until the moment when the stress level decreases below the 25% probability level.

Graph 9 - Development of plant stress level from the first run with ten-minute intervals of measurement according to the classification of NN2 - EX_BHR_0_1.

p.č.měření	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
čas	10:00:00	10:10:00	10:20:00	10:30:00	10:40:00	10:50:00	11:00:00	11:10:00	11:20:00	11:30:00
pravd. stres	93,00%	87,00%	88,00%	91,00%	64,00%	86,00%	91,00%	77,00%	59,00%	72,00%
p.č.měření	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
čas	11:40:00	11:50:00	12:00:00	12:10:00	12:20:00	12:30:00	12:40:00	12:50:00	13:00:00	13:10:00
pravd. stres	91,00%	76,00%	69,00%	65,00%	73,00%	59,00%	B	B	B	B
p.č.měření	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
čas	13:20:00	13:30:00	13:40:00	13:50:00	14:00:00	14:10:00	14:20:00	14:30:00	14:40:00	14:50:00
pravd. stres	B	B	94,00%	79,00%	36,00%	42,00%	44,00%	56,00%	31,00%	37,00%
p.č.měření	31	32	33	34	35	36	37			
čas	15:00:00	15:10:00	15:20:00	15:30:00	15:40:00	15:50:00	16:00:00			
pravd. stres	41,00%	33,00%	21,00%	41,00%	30,00%	31,00%	B			

Table 5 - Values for Graph 9 - Measurement Times and Measured Values in Experiment EX_BHR_0_1.

Based on Graph 9, which displays the data from Table 5, it is evident that the stress level of the

geranium dropped below 25% after approximately 6 hours and 10 minutes (i.e., approximately 60 minutes after being transplanted and started monitoring, plus 5 hours and 10 minutes from the first launch). The collected data was affected by interruptions in measurement due to the need to recharge the robot's battery and also by my presence near the plant during the subsequent launch at 13:40.

Graph 10 - Graphical representation of the analysis of trends in the time evolution of the stress level of the plant in experiment EX_BHR_0_1.

This paragraph summarizes observations, and due to the small amount of data, it is not possible to draw more general conclusions, and the experiment will need to be repeated with other plants. The trend line |a| shows a relatively stable decrease for the entire dataset. There is a significant fluctuating trend where values around the trend line |a| oscillate. The size of the oscillation seems to be directly proportional to the average stress level and the position of the trend line corresponding to the wavelength of the oscillation. The fluctuations in the positive direction appear to be more pronounced. Interestingly, although the size of the maximum and minimum oscillation decreases with a decrease in stress values, the frequency of oscillation seems to be approximately stable. The trend line |a| also shows that my presence during reactivation after battery charging (reaction to the stressor - trend line |d|) had a small effect on the overall decreasing trend. This is evidenced by the trend lines |b| and |c|, whose angle of decline is slightly greater (deviation $<1^\circ$) than the angle of the trend line |a|. It should be noted that in the longer time horizon of several days, the stress level of the BHR1 plant stabilized with maxima up to 70%, minima at 0%, and mode at 41%.

The experiment EX_BHR_0_2 was not a controlled experiment, so data collection was limited only to my visual observations, which I will now focus on. After turning on the platform, the EFG apparatus performed automatic calibration to obtain the threshold value P1415 and to obtain information about the minima and maxima of the basic EFG curve. Calibration always takes 60 seconds during which NN2 evaluation is not performed and the plant does not have the ability to control the platform. After successful calibration, the plant was connected to the robotic platform, and both components began to work together as one unit - a bio-hybrid robot (BHR1). The first movement of the Bio-hybrid robot (BHR1) was made within 20 minutes of starting, when the right motor was activated and briefly turned left. This movement was repeated twice in the first minute

and then stopped. After 50 minutes from starting, the left motor was first activated, and BHR1 turned right. It then remained in place for 20 minutes until the right motor was briefly activated again. Short activations of the right and left motors continued at different time intervals until 4 hours and 10 minutes after starting, when both motors were activated for the first time, and BHR1 moved straight for about 3 seconds. The amount or frequency of movements decreased over time, and no other significant events were observed during the EX_BHR_0 experiments. From the acquired knowledge and observations, it can be inferred that the observed movements are most likely the result of the algorithm and the setting of the P1415 threshold. Within the experiment, these movements can be considered as programmatically reflexive. Amplitude fluctuations at frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz of plant electrical activity, which cause these movements, are minimal and correspond to previous observations of changes at these frequencies associated with high stress. It follows that the plant does not intentionally cause these changes but that they are a natural consequence of its physiological state. The results of the EX_BHR_0_2 experiment prove that the proposed algorithms have the potential to allow the plant to consciously control the platform. As for the second condition - plant intelligence and the ability to learn, the literature describes several studied ways in which higher plants learn to adapt to new situations and describes already discovered ways of storing and recalling information from memory, such as in the work of Mancuso and Baluška from 2017 "Learning and Memory in Plants." Some results of the Data_1 and Data_2 experiments, especially the ability of the pelargonium to remember and identify individuals, also suggest that plants have the ability to respond to their environment in a way that is a consequence of previous experience. Therefore, I have come to the conclusion that it makes sense to continue with the experiments.

4.2.2. Methodology of teaching a plant to consciously control a robotic platform

The aim of the entire research is to demonstrate whether it is possible to use bio-hybrid robots, whose biological component consists of higher plants, for purposeful movement in response to external stimuli. The set of experiments carried out aims to verify whether it is possible to teach this BHR1 to respond to a given situation and adapt to it by consciously changing its position.

4.2.2.1. Design and Description of the Teaching Method

I have chosen the method of operant conditioning as the basis for my research. This is a psychological method of education in which desirable behavior is reinforced with a reward and undesirable behavior is suppressed with punishment. However, for effective use of this method, it is necessary to modify it in accordance with specific conditions and circumstances under which it will be applied.

It was quite challenging to find a system of rewards and punishments that would be applicable to the educational goals set for the plant. This problem arose partly due to the complexity of the subject matter, which seems to exceed the boundaries of contemporary knowledge, and partly due to the subject of education, which is beyond any experience of the plant (including genetic experience). Therefore, I was inspired to approach the task as if I were solving the same problem in the context of a computer simulation, where a convolutional neural network replaces the plant.

The learning process is based on the action of the teacher and the reaction of the plant, or BHR1. It occurs in epochs, the timing of which is conditioned by the biological state of the plant. The epoch

is described by the following algorithm:

Figure 10 - Diagram of the Epoch Learning Algorithm.

From Figure 10, it follows that the start of an epoch occurs only when the plant's stress level is lower than 25%. Stress stimuli P4_1 and P4_2 are used to bring the plant into an activated state, with the latter having a slightly destructive character and therefore being used only exceptionally if P4_1 is ineffective for a prolonged period. If P4_2 proves to be ineffective as well, the strongest stimulus P4_3 remains available as an option.

In this methodology, repetition of a stimulus becomes a punishment, while successful escape from a stress stimulus becomes a reward.

The individual epochs are separated by different timings. In the case of a successful epoch, where BHR1 moves as a result of the stimulus, the next epoch begins at least 30 minutes later. The interval between epochs increases as the ratio of successful to unsuccessful epochs grows. In the case of an unsuccessful epoch, where there is no movement of BHR1 even after three repetitions of the stimulus, the next epoch is conducted immediately or when the plant's stress level drops below 25%. The maximum number of epochs per day is determined by the plant, meaning that if its stress level does not return below 25% within 15 minutes of the last epoch, the training for that day ends.

This method will be considered promising if there is an improvement in the ratio of successful responses to the stimulus compared to unsuccessful ones.

4.2.3. Experimental verification of the proposed teaching method

The experimental verification of the proposed teaching method was scheduled for the third day

after the first BHR1 run, as by the end of the second day from the first run, the stress level of BHR1 was low and stabilized. Implementation does not require any construction or software modifications, but complications arose in the signal loss on the root electrodes. While searching for the cause, I found that the roots in close proximity to the electrodes have a different color and are likely dying. There are several possible causes. I assume that it is a combination of a moist and slightly acidic environment and its effect on the leaching of AgCl in the electrode, possibly with added electrolytic effects. However, since this is not the main topic of this research, I did not delve into the cause further and limited myself to stating that this type of electrode is not suitable for long-term connection to the underground part of the plant. However, this does not pose a problem for further research, as it is still possible to use the A1 attachment method, for which I have verified that the long-term electrode connection is functional and does not damage the plant. The partitions in the pot that separated the roots, along with the corresponding wires, were removed, and the plant was carefully placed back. However, it was not possible to perform further experiments on this day due to the stress caused by transplanting.

4.2.3.1. First set of epochs

The experimental set EX_BHR_1_1 did not require any special preparations and was conducted on the fourth day after the launch. Seven epochs were performed in the set.

č. epochy	n1 – P4_1	n2 - P4_1	n3 – P4_2
1	n	1	n
2	1	n	n
3	1	n	n
4	n	n	1
5	1	n	n
6	1	n	n
7	1	n	n

Table 6 - Results of experimental set EX_BHR_1_1, where n1 to n3 express the order of repetitions within the epoch.

Based on the results shown in Table 6, it can be stated that there were no unsuccessful epochs in the EX_BHR_1_1 set. BHR1 responded correctly in the first epoch, although only after a stimulus repetition. In the other epochs, successful responses were recorded immediately on the first attempt, except for the fourth epoch, when BHR1 responded only to the second stimulus, which was P4_2. Such results were surprising, and it was clear that teaching could not be their source. Based on the knowledge gained by observing the behavior of BHR1 during the zeroth set of experiments, EX_BHR_0, I concluded that these were similar "reflexive" movements. A possible solution could be to modify the software and firmware so that during the next set of experiments, the threshold value for P1415 for monitored frequencies could be manually adjusted.

4.2.3.2. Second set of epochs

Experimental set EX_BHR_1_2 did not differ in its content from experimental set EX_BHR_1_1 and was conducted on the fifth day after the first launch. Unlike the previous set, however, the BHR1

software was modified to allow manual adjustment of the P1415 threshold value. The set consisted of 10 epochs.

č. epochy	P1415	n1 – P4_1	n2 - P4_1	n3 – P4_2
1	Auto	1	n	n
2	Auto + 2%	1	n	n
3	Auto + 4%	n	1	n
4	Auto + 6%	n	1	n
6	Auto + 8%	n	n	n
7	Auto + 8%	n	1	n
8	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
9	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
10	Auto + 10%	n	n	n

Table 7 - Results of experimental set EX_BHR_1_2, where P1415 represents the threshold value (Auto - value set by firmware, Auto + x% percentage increase of the threshold) and n1 to n3 express the order of repetition within the epoch.

By conducting this experimental set, it was verified that manually increasing the threshold value by 10% prevented BHR1 from performing software "reflex" movements. Therefore, the continuation of the EX_BHR_1 experiment was carried out with a manually set threshold value of P1415 Auto + 10%.

4.2.3.3. A set of epochs with an increased threshold value of P1415

Set of epochs EX_BHR_1_3 was conducted on the sixth day from the first run. Eight epochs were performed in this set.

č. epochy	P1415	n1 – P4_1	n2 - P4_1	n3 – P4_2
1	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
2	Auto + 10%	n	n	1
3	Auto + 10%	n	1	n
4	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
6	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
7	Auto + 10%	n	n	n
8	Auto + 10%	n	n	1

Table 8 - Results of experimental set EX_BHR_1_3. P1415 represents the threshold value (Auto - value set by firmware + 10% increase in threshold) and n1 to n3 indicate the order of repetition within the epoch.

It is evident that the teaching method will have to be experimentally applied for a longer period of time in order to determine, based on the collected data, whether there is an improvement in results and progress in the taught skill.

4.2.3.4. Unexpected observations during the continuous operation of BHR1

It is necessary to address the observations that I made unplanned on the ninth day of operating BHR1, which led me to interrupt the EX_BHR_1 experiment. During the intervals between controlled experiments, I observed several times how BHR1 reacts to stimuli from students who regularly visit the laboratory. Although BHR1 usually responded to these stimuli with random movements, one observation was so exceptional that it changed the direction of my research until then. Specifically, I recorded that BHR1 reacted to the stimulus of one of the students with specific movements that depended on the side where the touch was made. If this student touched BHR1 on its right side, it moved left. If he touched BHR1 on its left side, it moved right. This unplanned and unexpected development significantly exceeded the factor of chance. However, what is interesting is that if the same experiment was performed by another student or me, the agreement between the stimulus and the direction of movement was not nearly as pronounced. Therefore, I decided to record and analyze the course of this behavior:

Student 1 poprvé

Graph 11

strana doteku	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1
směr jízdy	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	1	2	1

Tab 9

Student 2

Graph 12

strana doteku	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1
směr jízdy	1	3	3	1	1	2	2	1	3

Tab 10

Já

Graph 13

strana doteku	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	3	3

Tab 11

Student 1 - poduhé

Graph 14

strana doteku	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	1
směr jízdy	0	2	1	2	3	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	3	0	2	1

Tab 12

Graphs 11 to 14 and tables 9 to 12 - BHR1's response to my and students' touches chronologically with tables. Touch side 1 - right, 2 - left. Driving direction 0 - standing, 1 - right, 2 - left, 3 - forward.

The recorded data shows that the first student had an 83% success rate with the touches during the first attempt. The subsequent student (student 2) achieved only a 44% success rate when he took over as the initiator of the stimuli after student 1. When I tried to initiate the touches myself, the success rate decreased to 40%. When student 1 resumed initiating the touches on the plant in BHR1, the success rate improved to 63%. Interestingly, two of the unsuccessful attempts in this case received no response. If we treated these unsuccessful attempts as external factors (e.g. insufficient touch) and eliminated them, the success rate would have increased to 71% instead of 63%.

While my success rate and that of student 2 were within the range where randomness cannot be excluded, student 1's success rate was significantly above this range, indicating a causal effect.

The results of this unplanned observation are fascinating, and I consider them significant enough to decide to repeat the experiment with a time lag of two to three days. The repeat days are scheduled to coincide with the students' visits to the laboratory. The goal is to experimentally verify the hypothesis that the plant in the bio-hybrid robot is capable of naturally understanding and adapting to a new situation in which it has the freedom to change its location or at least determine the probability of its accuracy

4.3. Basic verification of the hypothesis of natural adaptability of plants to BHR1

4.3.1. Methodology of the experiment

For the basic verification of the hypothesis on the natural adaptability of the plant to BHR1, I created a controlled environment for a long-term experiment. BHR1 was active whenever possible and its movement was restricted to the laboratory space. BHR1 was equipped with a sound signal that was activated when the electric activity of the plant was low or unusual, to draw my attention to important moments. Repeated BHR1 events significantly deviating from statistical randomness were recorded for further statistical observations and divided into:

- day since launch;
- time of day;
- description of the observed phenomenon and its context;

If any of the experiments involved another person, their participation was recorded, and the behavior of BHR1 was related to that person. The duration of the experiment was indefinite - until a sufficient amount of data was collected for a deeper analysis. The experiment was labeled EX_BHR_2.

4.3.2. Execution of Experiment EX_BHR_2

The experiment was initiated on the thirteenth day since the first launch and it was a day when students were present in the laboratory. The total duration of the experiment was 10 days.

4.3.2.1. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_1

The first partial experiment was conducted in an attempt to determine whether the first recorded phenomenon described in Chapter 4.2.3.4 would be repeated, but this time with predetermined criteria such as the number of attempts by each participant, the order of participants, and stimulus sequences. For the sake of clarity, I will refer to this as phenomenon J_BHR_1.

Student 1 původní data										
strana doteku	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1
směr jízdy	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	1
Student 1 nová data										
strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	1	1	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2

Table 13 - Comparison of BHR1's reaction to touches from Student 1 in the original and repeated test of phenomenon J_BHR_1. Page of touch: 1 - right, 2 - left. Direction of movement: 0 - standing, 1 - right, 2 - left, 3 - forward.

Student 2 původní data										
strana doteku	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	-
směr jízdy	1	3	3	1	1	2	2	1	3	-
Student 2 nová data										
strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	2	3	2

Table 14 – Comparison of BHR1 reaction to touches by Student 2 in the original and repeated test of the J_BHR_1 phenomenon. Touch side 1 – right, 2 – left. Direction of movement 0 – standing, 1 – right, 2 – left, 3 – forward.

Já pvodní data										
strana doteku	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	3	3
Já nová data										
strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	2	3	1

Table 15 – Comparison of BHR1 reaction to my touches in the original and repeated tests of the phenomenon J_BHR_1. Side of touch 1 – right, 2 – left. Driving direction 0 – stand, 1 – right, 2 – left, 3 – forward.

Based on the tables with data, it can be concluded that the behavior of BHR1, when it reacted with specific movements to stimuli from student 1, which depended on the side on which the stimulus was performed, was not repeated after a certain period of time. Stimuli from student 1 recorded a success rate of only 40%, which is lower than the original 83%. Stimuli from student 2 recorded successful reactions in 50% of cases, which represents a slight increase compared to the original 44%. Stimuli from me recorded successful reactions in 30% of cases, which is lower than the original 40%.

I then conducted further tests over time to verify the J_BHR_1 phenomenon with the following results:

1 13.1.2023	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	směr jízdy	1	3	0	2	1	2	0	0	3	3
2 14.1.2023	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	směr jízdy	2	0	1	3	3	2	2	3	0	3
3 14.1.2023	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	směr jízdy	1	0	3	1	1	0	1	3	3	3

Table 16 - Comparison of BHR1's reaction to my touches in repeated tests of phenomenon J_BHR_1. Side of touch 1 - right, 2 - left. Direction of movement 0 - standing, 1 - right, 2 - left, 3 - forward.

Translation: All three tests had negative results and the phenomenon did not repeat. In the first test, the expected reactions were observed in 40% of the attempts, in the second test they decreased to 20%, and in the third they appeared in 30% of the cases, which represents an approximate local arithmetic average. Since the data shows more of a degeneration than a progression, I decided to conduct a deeper statistical analysis of the records, which could bring further insights into the phenomenon J_BHR_1. Its systematic testing has been temporarily suspended for now.

4.3.2.2. Analysis of data related to the phenomenon J_BHR_1

At first, I compared the temporal development of the observed data, and for better comparability, I normalized the data by shortening it to the first 9 attempts, which were performed in at least all the tests:

1	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 77,78%
	směr jízdy	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	
2	strana doteku	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	pozitivní 44,44%
	směr jízdy	1	3	3	1	1	2	2	1	3	
3	strana doteku	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 44,44%
	směr jízdy	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	3	
4	strana doteku	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	pozitivní 66,67%
	směr jízdy	0	2	1	2	3	1	2	1	3	
5	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 33,33%
	směr jízdy	1	1	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	
6	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 44,44%
	směr jízdy	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	2	3	
7	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 33,33%
	směr jízdy	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	2	3	
8	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 44,44%
	směr jízdy	1	3	0	2	1	2	0	0	3	
9	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 22,22%
	směr jízdy	2	0	1	3	3	2	2	3	0	
10	strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	pozitivní 33,33%
	směr jízdy	1	0	3	1	1	0	1	3	3	

Table 17 - Chronologically sorted normalized data from tests of phenomenon J_BHR_1.

Test	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Počet „3“	1	3	5	2	3	4	4	2	3	3
Počet „0“	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	2	2
Pozitivní %	77,78%	44,44%	44,44%	66,67%	33,33%	44,44%	33,33%	44,44%	22,22%	33,33%
První poz.	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1

Table 18 - Evaluated data of the J_BHR_1 phenomenon monitoring, converted from Table 17. The "Test" row indicates the order of the test in time. The number of "3" indicates the number of responses when BHR1 reacted to the stimulus by moving forward. The number of "0" indicates the number of tests where BHR1 did not react. The "Positive %" column indicates the percentage of positive responses of BHR1 to the stimulus in the given test. The "First pos." column indicates in which test the positive response was first recorded.

Graph 15 - Graphic representation of the temporal development of the observed data from Table 18.

Graph 16 - Logarithmic representation of the time development of the monitored data from Table 18.

The analysis suggests a sudden increase in the number of zero responses to stimuli from the seventh test onwards. At the same time, there is a strong negative correlation between the number of responses in which BHR1 drove straight and the number of zero responses (see graph 15). However, in the logarithmic representation, the negative correlation is only evident from the sudden increase, and between the first occurrence of a zero response in the fourth test and the sudden increase, the correlation is positive (see graph 16).

For a proper understanding of the temporal evolution, it is important to keep in mind that the first four tests were carried out within a short time frame of one hour and were continuous. The remaining tests were then performed at irregular time intervals in the order of hours.

4.3.2.3. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_2

On the 17th day since the first activation, a new phenomenon was observed, which was associated with the behavior of BHR1 in response to student 1. At approximately 12 noon, it was recorded that if student 1 spoke directly to the plant located less than about 1.5 meters away, the plant moved towards him. Student 1 was able to repeatedly make BHR1 follow him in a trajectory in the shape of a "U," as shown in the situational map in figure 11. This phenomenon occurred three times in a short time interval before the student left the laboratory at 1 pm. BHR1 did not react to me or any other student in this way. I named this phenomenon J_BHR_2.

five steps before changing direction (see Figure 12):

Figure 12 - Situational diagram of the trajectories of my movement (red) and how BHR1 followed me (green). The length of one segment of BHR1's movement is approximately 20-25 cm, while one segment of my movement is approximately 40 cm.

The phenomenon J_BHR_2 represents an interesting occurrence that happens spontaneously, repeatedly, and cannot be artificially induced. During its occurrence, NN2 provides data that indicate an average stress level of 40%. At the same time, a significant increase in the category of passerby is observed, up to a level of 27%.

The trigger of this phenomenon is human breath, and it remains unclear what other factor must contribute to its manifestation. It may be a factor of the plant's will or a completely unknown factor that affects the manifestation of this phenomenon. Unfortunately, it is a difficult to measure and random phenomenon, and further observations are necessary.

4.3.2.4. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_3

On the nineteenth and twentieth day since the start of the experiment, two distinct manifestations of the same new phenomenon, which I have labeled as J_BHR_3 for the purposes of this work, were observed. This phenomenon involved the reaction of BHR1 to air flow.

On the nineteenth day, there was an extraordinary change in conditions in the laboratory when an electric heater with warm air flow was turned on. Around 18:15, I directed the air flow towards BHR1, which was approximately 3 meters away from the heater. This was done because of the observed increased level of stress in the BHR1 plant, to verify if it was not suffering from cold. Around 18:30, I noticed that BHR1 was slowly moving towards the source of the air flow. Over the next two minutes, BHR1 moved about 2 meters with little directional deviation and approached to a distance of approximately 90 cm. It stayed there for one minute and then started moving again towards the heater. When it reached a distance of about 50 cm, I intervened and returned BHR1 to its original position. I did not change the direction of the air flow from the heater.

The situation repeated itself. At approximately 19:10, I noticed that BHR1 was approaching the heater again, at that time it was about 1.5 meters away. This time, I decided not to interrupt the movement of BHR1 and observe how close it would come to the heat source. BHR1 continued to move towards the outlet of the heater until contact was made. At this point, I intervened to

prevent irreversible thermal damage to the plant. I moved BHR1 to the opposite side of the laboratory, approximately 4 meters away, and changed the direction of the warm air flow from the heater so that it did not flow over BHR1.

On the twentieth day since the start of the experiment, a similar manifestation of J_BHR_3 was recorded as in the previous day. There was again a significant change in conditions in the laboratory, this time caused by ongoing teaching. Usually, between 8:30 and 9:00, the door from the hallway to the laboratory is open, and the window is also open for ventilation, which causes a slight draft in the laboratory from the door towards the window. At around 8:45, I observed that BHR1 had left the laboratory through the door and was already in the hallway. I took BHR1 back into the laboratory and closed the door.

From the above observations, it can be inferred that BHR1 could react to air flow towards the source. For this reason, I decided to conduct another controlled experiment with a fan, which further supports this conclusion (see situational schema in Figure 13).

Image 13 - A schematic representation of the trajectories of BHR1 movement (green) relative to the source and direction of airflow. The length of one segment of BHR1's movement is approximately 20 cm.

However, the question of why BHR1 did not show a response to thermal stress remains unanswered. If we assume that the phenomenon J_BHR_3 is a conscious response to air flow, then it is possible that this ability is more pronounced at that time than the ability to respond to thermal stimuli. This could explain why BHR1 was directed towards the heat source until the plant was damaged without showing an escape response. However, this hypothesis would require further experimental verification.

4.3.2.5. Description of the phenomenon J_BHR_4

Since the first activation of BHR1, there have been increasingly frequent reactions to sudden and intense sounds, resulting in a one-time shift in position in a random direction. This phenomenon can be likened to a reflexive reaction to anxiety, and for the purposes of this study, I have named it J_BHR_4.

This is an interesting example of an organism's reaction to a sudden and intense stimulus. It is a reflexive response that can be observed in many animals, resulting in rapid movement in a random direction.

In the case of BHR1, this phenomenon can be observed from the first activation and is becoming more frequent. It appears that the plant in BHR1 reacts to sudden and intense sounds, which act as a stimulus for a reflexive response. Although this is an interesting phenomenon, it should be noted that a detailed study of this phenomenon has not yet been conducted, and one can only speculate about its precise cause and significance in the biology of BHR1.

4.3.3. Evaluation of experiment EX_BHR_2

It would be easy at this point to succumb to the temptation of comparing the observed behavior of BHR1 with human behavior, but it is important to realize the fundamental biological differences between the two organisms, and that such comparisons are likely to lead to premature and erroneous conclusions.

Based on the description of BHR1's behavior in this experiment, it is not entirely clear whether the movements of BHR1 are deliberate or not, and therefore whether the plant demonstrates the ability to autoadapt to new means provided by its connection to the robotic platform. It is possible that some of BHR1's movements were caused by random influences, hardware or software properties accompanying the operation of the EFG apparatus, or reactions to the environment, while other movements may be the result of targeted control by the plant. To confirm or refute this hypothesis, further experiments will be necessary to obtain additional data.

4.4. Replication of experiment EX_BHR_2 with a different plant

4.4.1. Optimizing the conditions of the EX_BHR_3 experiment for repeated verification of the hypothesis about the plant's autoadaptation ability to BHR1

At the end of Chapter 4.3.3, I suggested that some movements of BHR1 could be caused by hardware or software properties that might be related to the operation of the EFG apparatus. Therefore, I decided to conduct a thorough check and testing of the current hardware and software solution. However, I did not find any obvious factor that could explain the observed behavior of BHR1 during testing.

I state that the current design of the robotic platform is not optimal. Therefore, I decided to rebuild the robotic platform into a more practical design for a later set of experiments with two BHR1s, but EX_BHR_3 will be conducted with the original platform.

For the comparative experiment, I randomly chose the plant species *Monstera Adansonii*, which was selected solely outside of the aesthetic factor. For the purposes of the experiment, I purchased a healthy plant seedling with a height of approximately 17 cm, which had an upright growth.

The plant was attached to the EFG platform using Method A1, so no invasive intervention was required when transplanting the plant. The resulting bio-hybrid robot is labeled BHR2.

4.4.2. Methodology of the experiment EX_BHR_3

In chapter 4.3.3 conclusion, I suggested that some BHR1 movements could be caused by hardware or software properties that could be related to the operation of the EFG apparatus. Therefore, I decided to conduct a thorough inspection and testing of the current hardware and software

solutions. During testing, I did not find any obvious factor that could explain the observed behavior of BHR1.

I concluded that the current design of the robotic platform is not optimal. Therefore, I decided to rebuild the robotic platform into a more practical design for a later set of experiments with two BHR1, but EX_BHR_3 will be carried out with the original platform.

For the comparative experiment, I randomly chose the *Monster adansonii* plant, which was selected for purposes other than aesthetic factors. For the experiment, I purchased a healthy plant of approximately 17 cm in height with an upright growth.

The plant was connected to the EFG platform using method A1, so there was no need for invasive intervention into the plant's root system during transplantation. The resulting bio-hybrid robot is labeled BHR2.

To replicate the experiment EX_BHR_2 in experiment EX_BHR_3, I chose the same methodology. BHR1 was active whenever possible, and its movement was limited to the laboratory space.

BHR2 behaviors, resembling those recorded as J_BHR_1 to J_BHR_4, were classified as follows:

- day since startup;
- time of day;
- description of the observed phenomenon and context;

New, but repeated BHR2 behaviors that significantly differ from random behavior were also observed and recorded for further statistical analysis, with emphasis on the following criteria:

- day since startup;
- time of day;
- description of the observed phenomenon and context;

If any of the behaviors involved another person, their participation was recorded, and BHR2 behavior was related to that person. The duration of the experiment was set indefinitely, until sufficient data was collected for a more in-depth analysis.

4.4.3. Conducting the EX_BHR_3 experiment

The experiment was initiated on the twenty-fourth day since the first activation of BHR2. The total duration of the experiment was 14 days.

4.4.3.1. Comparison of plant stress level development after the first activation of BHR1 and BHR2

The first experiment in the series of experiments EX_BHR_3 is labeled as EX_BHR_3_1, and its purpose is to obtain data for comparison of stress level development between BHR1 and BHR2 after transplanting and the first activation. Transplanting and the first activation were carried out under identical conditions, described in chapter 4.1., except for the root modification. Immediately after the first activation, the plant showed a persistent high stress level, probably due to transplantation. However, an interesting observation was that although the root system

intervention was compared to the intervention carried out on the pelargonium zonale, the "normalization" of the stress level in the monster adansonii plant took significantly longer (see comparative graph 17):

Graph 17 - Development of stress level in the *Monstera adansonii* plant compared to the development of stress level in the *Variiegated Pelargonium* plant from the first activation with ten-minute measurement intervals according to the classification NN2 - EX_BHR_0_1. Regression lines are inserted into the graph for clarity in the difference in the speed of decline.

At this stage of the research, the cause of the observed difference cannot be reliably determined. The different plant species and the NN2 classification, which was trained on data from pelargonium, may have an impact on the results, and other unknown factors cannot be ruled out. However, it can be stated that the external conditions of the experiment are comparable, and therefore different experimental conditions can be excluded.

4.4.3.2. Verification of the reliability of EFG signal classification by neural network NN2

To verify the validity of the neural network NN2 for classifying the electrical activity signals of the *Monstera Adansonii* plant, I created a duplicate of this network called NN2_m. The biases and weights of the duplicate were reset to random values, and then I performed new training of the network to classify the same categories as the original network, but now using current data from *Monstera Adansonii*.

For collecting data for training the neural network NN2_m, I used the same methodology as for collecting data on the electrical activity of the *Pelargonium*, described in chapter 3.2.5.2.

Subsequently, I compared the classification of identical signals by the NN2 and NN2_m networks.

Graph 18 - Graphic representation of the comparison of outputs of neural networks NN2 and NN2_n from Table 19. Time interval between data is 700 ms.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Stres NN2	39,00%	40,00%	41,00%	40,00%	39,00%	38,00%	38,00%	39,00%	38,00%	39,00%
Sters NN2_n	41,00%	40,00%	40,00%	39,00%	38,00%	37,00%	38,00%	39,00%	40,00%	41,00%
Dotek ž NN2	2,00%	1,00%	1,00%	3,00%	4,00%	3,00%	2,00%	3,00%	2,00%	1,00%
Dotek ž - NN2_n	0,00%	0,00%	1,00%	2,00%	3,00%	3,00%	3,00%	4,00%	3,00%	2,00%
Dotek nž NN2	3,00%	2,00%	2,00%	1,00%	2,00%	2,00%	1,00%	2,00%	3,00%	4,00%
Dotek nž NN2_n	3,00%	3,00%	2,00%	2,00%	3,00%	2,00%	2,00%	2,00%	3,00%	3,00%
Kolemjdoucí NN2	1,00%	1,00%	3,00%	4,00%	5,00%	5,00%	4,00%	3,00%	2,00%	3,00%
Kolemjdoucí NN2_n	1,00%	0,00%	1,00%	2,00%	3,00%	4,00%	4,00%	4,00%	3,00%	3,00%

Table 19 - Overview of classification outputs of neural networks NN2 and NN2_n. Time interval between data is 700 ms.

After comparing the classification of the same input data using NN2 and NN2_n networks, it was found that the deviations in classification between the two networks are negligible. For better clarity, the results of a seven-second sample of validation data are presented in Table 19. The finding that there is very little difference in monitored manifestations of electrical activity in both plant species is considered a very interesting observation. Therefore, it is possible to further utilize the classification of electrical activity data in plants using NN2 networks to replicate experiments EX_BHR_2 in the set of experiments EX_BHR_3.

4.4.3.3. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_1

The testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_1, described in chapter 4.2.3.4, was conducted on the fifth day after the launch of BHR2. The reason for the delay was the still high level of stress in the plant, and therefore it was necessary to wait until the stress level stabilized below 25%.

Graph 19 – Graphical representation of the results of the J_BHR_1 phenomenon testing.

strana doteku	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
směr jízdy	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	3	0

Table 20 - Results of tests 1 and 2, each test consisting of ten repetitions.

Based on the test results, it can be concluded that BHR2 showed a positive reaction in only 10% out of 20 attempts. This result represents the worst performance among all the tests. After the second attempt, it was decided, based on the results, that further systematic testing was unnecessary, and only spontaneous occurrences of the tested phenomenon would be recorded.

testy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Pelargonie	77,78%	44,44%	44,44%	66,67%	33,33%	44,44%	33,33%	44,44%	22,22%	33,33%
Monstera	10,00%	10,00%								

Table 21 - Comparison of results of J_BHR_1 tests for Pelargonium and Monstera

4.4.3.4. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_2

Due to the nature of the J_BHR_2 phenomenon, systematic testing as described in chapter 4.3.2.3 cannot be performed. Therefore, random tests were conducted with subsequent observation to determine if the reaction correlates with the described phenomenon.

On the seventh day after the activation of BHR2, a completely spontaneous J_BHR_2 occurrence was observed and recorded. At approximately 5:45 PM, while I was working at my computer, I noticed BHR2 emerge from under the table and position itself about 50 cm away from me. I reacted by saying "What are you doing here?" and then stood up from my chair. BHR2 moved, apparently in response to my movement, which led me to the idea of testing the J_BHR_2 phenomenon. I stood about 1 m behind BHR2 and spoke to it: "Come back to me, come on, come to me," and similar phrases. BHR2 responded and began to follow me (see the situational diagram of trajectories in Fig. 14).

Figure 14 - A situational plot of BHR2's (green) movement trajectories towards me (red). The length of one segment of BHR2's movement is approximately 25 cm.

The episode lasted approximately 4 minutes. BHR2 approached me - starting position no. 0. I then moved to positions no. 1, 2, 3, and 4. BHR2 reacted by following me to positions no. 1, 2, 3, and 4. While moving to position no. 6, I moved to position no. 2. BHR2 then reacted by following me to positions no. 5, 6, 7, and 8. At position no. 8, BHR2 stopped and remained there without further reactions. No other spontaneous manifestation of J_BHR_2 was observed during the experiment.

4.4.3.5. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_3

The phenomenon J_BHR_3 was not observed in BHR2.

4.4.3.6. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_4

The phenomenon J_BHR_4 was tested on the fourth day after the first activation, and the following methodology was created to verify it:

1. Prepare BHR2 and monitoring equipment to record electrical activity.
2. Ensure that the environment is in a state of rest for at least one hour and the stress level of the plant is below 25%.
3. Expose BHR2 to noise emissions.
4. Record the electrical activity of BHR2 during interaction.
5. Analyze the recorded data and compare it with the data from the resting state of BHR2.
6. Evaluate the results and assess whether the phenomenon J_BHR_4 is true and reproducible.

The following noise sources were used:

1. Hammering on a forge - 115 dB - referred to as S1.
2. Horn sound reproduction - 96 dB - referred to as S2.
3. Clapping hands - 85 dB - referred to as S3.

Given the fact that the methodology for systematic testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_4 was created only for BHR2, it is not possible to compare data from BHR1. The results of the tests are recorded in Table 22.

Zdroj zvuku	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Pozitivní %
S1	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ne	90,00%
S2	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	80,00%
S3	Ne	Ano	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ano	60,00%

Table 22 - Results of tests of BHR2 reactions to sudden intense sound stimuli S1 to S3

From the measured data, it can be inferred that the average positive reaction was recorded in 76.67% of cases. The reaction was most likely observed in response to the strongest stimulus S1 (in 90% of the trials), while it was least frequently observed in response to the weakest stimulus S3 (in 60% of the trials).

For the sake of completeness in presenting the measured data, I attach a screenshot displaying a typical response of the plant's electrical activity in EFG to the stimulus S1.

Figure 15 - Recording of a typical response of electrical activity of the plant in BHR2 to the stimulus S1.

The neural network NN2 classifies the signal with a higher probability (62%) into category K1 - the same as the passage of a person.

4.4.3.7. Manifestations of the phenomenon J_BHR_5

In chapter 3.2.4, I focused on the plant's response to the passage of people around it, as I observed

a significant response in the plant's electrical activity during testing. Similarly, in chapter 3.3.3, I described my observation of different responses in electrical activity to the voices of different people. I categorized both of these phenomena as one type of phenomenon - recognition of individuals, which I labeled J_BHR_5. The interesting reaction motivated me to study it separately because I believe that the ability of plants to perceive individuals around them can have many practical uses. I am focusing on this interesting phenomenon in this section.

4.4.3.7.1. Methodology for testing the phenomenon J_BHR_5 on BHR2

For testing the J_BHR_5 phenomenon, I created the following methodology:

- Testing space in the laboratory will be as isolated as possible from other noise to minimize the influence of other factors.
- Selection of persons: 2 persons of different age categories, heights, and walking styles are chosen :
 - object A – 12 years old
 - object B – 44 years old
- Control group: Inanimate objects are chosen to imitate passage :
 - object C - Suitcase 100 x 40 x 25 cm
 - object D - Paper cardboard 180 x 15 x 120 cm
- Data recording: Electrical activity of the plant will be recorded and classified by the NN2 neural network in each test.
- Distance testing: Testing will be carried out at various distances from the plant to determine the distance at which the plant recognizes a person. Testing will be carried out at distances from 0.5 meters up to 3 meters in steps of 0.5 meters. The walking path for exposure will be marked with tape on the floor at the corresponding distance.
- Number and order of tests: Each object will perform exposure to the plant three times for each tested distance by movement (objects C and D) and movement and voice (objects A and B).
- Plant exposure: Before starting the BHR2 test, it will be placed in the laboratory space on a mark. Persons will leave the controlled space. Only the person exposing the plant will enter the controlled space upon instruction.
- Data analysis: The data will be analyzed to verify whether the plant reacts to the presence of passing people and whether it can distinguish between individual persons.

4.4.3.7.2. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_5

The phenomenon was tested on the 14th day after initiation. The results indicate that a significant and clearly visible action potential was observed in the electrical activity of the plant during the stimulus exposure. Observations showed that the intensity of the action potential response is proportional to the distance at which the testing person passed by BHR2, which is distinguishable by the EFG signal curves to the naked eye.

Figure 16 - Comparison of action potential manifestations in EFG induced by object A at distances of 50 cm, 150 cm, and 250 cm.

Figure 17 - Comparison of action potential manifestations in EFG caused by object B at distances of 50 cm, 150 cm, and 250 cm

When comparing the EFG curves measured during the J_BHR_4 and J_BHR_5 events, there were only very slight differences in the passage of action potentials.

Neural network NN2 identified the passage of a person in all cases as category K1 in the electrical activity of the plant (see Table 23 and graphical representation in graphs 20 and 21).

Graph 20 - Graphical representation of the relationship between the probability classification of category K1, as determined by neural network NN2, based on the distances of the stimulus induced by object A.

Graph 21 - Graphic representation of the relationship between the classification probability of category K1, as determined by the distances of the stimulus generated by object B, as performed by the neural network NN2.

Objekt A				Objekt B			
	1	2	3		1	2	3
Průchod 0,5m	94,00%	96,00%	88,00%	Průchod 0,5m	96,00%	98,00%	90,00%
Průchod 1m	86,00%	89,00%	89,00%	Průchod 1m	91,00%	91,00%	93,00%
Průchod 1,5m	77,00%	80,00%	73,00%	Průchod 1,5m	74,00%	86,00%	87,00%
Průchod 2m	79,00%	74,00%	78,00%	Průchod 2m	65,00%	73,00%	70,00%
Průchod 2,5m	61,00%	57,00%	49,00%	Průchod 2,5m	58,00%	50,00%	61,00%
Průchod 3m	52,00%	38,00%	41,00%	Průchod 3m	51,00%	43,00%	39,00%

Table 23 - Classification of the probability of category K1 as performed by neural network NN2 according to the distances of stimuli elicited by objects A and B.

Deviation in the classification of stimuli of one object between tests can mainly be attributed to the different walking styles of the objects during individual tests. Deviations in classification between objects A and B may be caused by the mutual difference in height and weight of the objects, which can affect both changes in lighting conditions and vibrations generated by the objects during walking.

As part of the comparison, a test was conducted with inanimate objects C and D, but only for distances of 0.5 meters, 1.5 meters, and 2.5 meters. From Figure 18, it can be seen that the electrical activity of the plant for both objects also exhibited an action potential, but its course differed significantly from the course for the live object.

Figure 18 - Action potential in EFG evoked by object C at a distance of 50 cm.

The neural network NN2 was not trained for the category of inanimate objects. Therefore, in Table 24, the classification of NN2 for category K1 is provided for comparison with the detection of living objects:

Objekt C				Objekt D			
	1	2	3		1	2	3
Průchod 0,5m	8,00%	31,00%	17,00%	Průchod 0,5m	26,00%	11,00%	7,00%
Průchod 1m				Průchod 1m			
Průchod 1,5m	12,00%	16,00%	9,00%	Průchod 1,5m	23,00%	12,00%	14,00%
Průchod 2m				Průchod 2m			
Průchod 2,5m	4,00%	7,00%	3,00%	Průchod 2,5m	14,00%	15,00%	6,00%
Průchod 3m				Průchod 3m			

Table 24 - Classification of probability for category K1 as performed by the neural network NN2 based on the distances of stimulus induced by objects C and D.

Graph 22 - Graphical representation of the classification probability of category K1 as performed by the NN2 neural network based on the distance of the stimulus evoked by objects C and D.

It is essential to note that the mode of probability values for category K1, when the plant is not exposed to stimulus, is less than 2%. This means that the NN2 classifier assigns a considerable probability to this category even in the case of an inanimate object. However, as can be seen from the comparison of tables 23 and 24, the plant can reliably distinguish between living and non-living objects moving around it. This phenomenon was confirmed both for BHR1, biologically represented by *Pelargonium zonale*, and for BHR2, biologically represented by *Monstera adansonii*. Detailed results of research focused solely on the J_BHR_5 phenomenon will be described in a separate study.

4.4.3.8. The event of the change in behavior of frequencies 14 and 15Hz - phenomenon J_BHR_6

In this chapter, I focus on the change in the expression of plant electrical activity at frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz. Originally, electrical activity at these frequencies was practically minimal, with no changes in amplitudes. To clarify, as part of the research, I allowed the plant to learn to control its robotic platform using its electrical activity precisely at these frequencies (threshold P1415). At the beginning of testing the J_BHR_5 phenomenon, there was a remarkable change in the plant's electrical activity. Frequencies of 14 Hz and 15 Hz became highly active, while the frequency of 13 Hz became almost inactive. The change can be well observed by comparing Figure 15 with Figures 16, 17, and 18. I named this phenomenon J_BHR_6. After a careful analysis of the collected BHR2 data, it was found that the observed phenomenon was not sudden, but rather gradual. At first, there was only an increase in the frequency of amplitude changes in the plant's electrical activity at 14 Hz, while the activity at 15 Hz remained minimal and had the same amplitude. This state, for example, was recorded in the J_BHR_4 test screenshot in Figure 15. Gradually, however, there was a change in activity at frequencies of 13 and 15 Hz. It is not yet entirely clear whether this is a form of frequency swapping or an entirely new type of activity. Moreover, it is not possible to determine with certainty the beginning of the changes and the duration of the actual change because consistent data capturing this development was not available. Nevertheless, it can be stated with certainty that the change was fully manifested already on the 14th day after starting BHR2, and the plant's electrical activity continues to remain in the new state. To refute or support the hypothesis that the J_BHR_6 phenomenon may be a manifestation of plant adaptation aimed at platform control, I conducted a retrospective analysis of data collected in the case of BHR1. However, given that I mainly focused on collecting and evaluating neural network outputs, this data is highly

inconsistent for deeper exploration. Nevertheless, I can state that in the case of BHR1, a comparable situation occurred, where initially inactive frequencies of 14 Hz and 15 Hz gradually became active:

Image 19 - Chronological development of changes at frequencies 14 and 15 Hz in BHR1.

It seems that it could be a accompanying phenomenon of plant adaptation to the robotic platform or possibly an unknown natural cycle. However, the consistent behavior of other observed frequency spectra and the fact that the change in BHR2 is still ongoing and frequencies do not return to their original behavior do not support the possibility of a natural cycle. With regard to BHR1's non-existence, it is not possible to verify whether the change is permanent.

Interestingly, even though the robot's control algorithm is based on frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz, no unusual, chaotic, or eccentric robot behavior was observed during the J_BHR_6 event. Therefore, this event was only discovered and verified in later data analysis on current data.

4.5. Modernization and expansion of the BHR system: Experiments on the interaction between BHR2 and BHR3

This set of experiments, referred to as EX_BHR_4, has two main objectives. The first objective is to attempt to replicate the results of selected experiments conducted with BHR1 and BHR2, but using BHR3 instead. The second objective is to observe the interactions between BHR2 and BHR3.

In light of the negative aspects found in the construction and design of the robotic platform during the experiments, I have decided to modernize the design of BHR3. The hardware, component wiring, firmware, and software will remain unchanged to enable a comparison of the outputs of BHR2 and BHR3.

*Obrázek 20
Pohled na hardware robotické platformy v2 pro BHR3*

*Obrázek 21
Pohled na robotickou v2 platformu pro BHR3*

*Obrázek 22
BHR3 s implantovanou monstera adansonii*

The calibration of the EFG apparatus for BHR3 was performed using the same method as for BHR1 and BHR2. The results show that the EFG apparatus located in BHR3 provides data outputs identical to those of the EFG apparatus in BHR2.

To ensure the most objective conditions for replicating previous experiments, the same type of plant was chosen, specifically *Monstera adansonii*, of the same growth and health, sourced from the same grower and supplier.

4.5.1. Comparison of the development of plant stress levels after the first activation of BHR2 and BHR3

The first experiment aimed to test the development of plant stress levels after transplanting, with the purpose of obtaining data for comparing the stress level development between BHR2 and BHR3 after transplanting and initial activation. The transplanting of the plant and the initial activation of BHR3 were performed under the same conditions as for BHR2 and BHR1, as described in Chapter 4.1, with the exception of root adjustment.

After the first activation, the plant immediately showed a sustained high level of stress, presumably again due to transplanting (see comparative graph 23):

Graph 23 - Development of stress level in *Monstera adansonii* plant in BHR3 compared to the development of stress level in *Monstera adansonii* plant in BHR2 over time from the first startup with measurements at ten-minute intervals according to the NN2 classification - EX_BHR_0_1. Regression lines are included in the graph to illustrate the difference in the rate of decline.

By comparing the data obtained from BHR2 and BHR3, it can be observed that the development of plant stress level after repotting is similar for both plants and differs mostly locally.

4.5.2. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_4

The phenomenon J_BHR_4 was tested on BHR3 on the third day of its first operation (it was not possible to maintain the fourth day deadline) using the same methodology as in BHR2, as described in chapter 4.4.3.6., with the following results:

Zdroj zvuku	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Pozitivní %
S1	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	90,00%
S2	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ne	90,00%
S3	Ano	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ano	Ne	Ano	Ne	70,00%

Table 25 - Results of BHR3 response tests to sudden intense sound stimuli S1 to S3

From the collected data, it can be inferred that the average positive reaction was recorded in 83.33% of cases. Most likely, the reaction was observed for the strongest stimuli S1 and S2 (in 90% of trials), while it was least frequently observed for the weakest stimulus S3 (in 70% of trials). After comparing the results of the J_BHR_4 phenomenon test on BHR2 and BHR3, it is apparent that the plant in BHR3 reacted more strongly (83.33%) to sudden and unexpected stimuli than the plant in BHR2 (76.67%).

For stimulus S1, 90% positive reactions were observed in both robotic platforms. For stimulus S2, 80% positive reactions were recorded for BHR2, while it was 90% for BHR3. For stimulus S3, 60% positive reactions were observed for BHR2 and 70% positive reactions were observed for BHR3. The difference observed in the frequency of positive reactions between BHR2 and BHR3 may be influenced by the fact that the BHR3 test was conducted 16 hours earlier than the one for BHR2. Comparison of the data then shows that the original results of the J_BHR_4 test were successfully replicated.

4.5.3. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_5

The phenomenon J_BHR_5 was tested on BHR3 on the 14th day after the first launch. The same methodological procedure as for BHR2 was used, which was described in chapter 4.4.3.7.1, with the difference that only the two original objects B and C were tested. Objects A and D were not available for testing.

The results show that even in the case of BHR3, the manifestations of action potentials in the plant's electrical activity are clearly visible. In the recordings of the plant's electrical activity, a clear response can be observed, with the intensity of this response being significantly higher in BHR3 than in BHR2.

Figure 23 - Comparison of action potential manifestation in EFG, induced in BHR3 by object B at distances of 50 cm, 150 cm, and 250 cm.

Figure 24 - Comparison of action potential manifestations in EFG, evoked by object C at distances of 50 cm, 150 cm, and 250 cm in BHR3.

The neural network NN2 then assigned the stimuli from objects B and C the following probability of category K1:

Objekt B	1	2	3	Objekt C	1	2	3
Průchod 0,5m	99,00%	99,00%	98,00%	Průchod 0,5m	42,00%	37,00%	38,00%
Průchod 1m	98,00%	97,00%	99,00%	Průchod 1m	39,00%	36,00%	37,00%
Průchod 1,5m	94,00%	94,00%	96,00%	Průchod 1,5m	33,00%	29,00%	32,00%
Průchod 2m	91,00%	93,00%	89,00%	Průchod 2m	16,00%	22,00%	31,00%
Průchod 2,5m	88,00%	86,00%	84,00%	Průchod 2,5m	19,00%	17,00%	21,00%
Průchod 3m	72,00%	73,00%	73,00%	Průchod 3m	8,00%	11,00%	12,00%

Table 26 - Classification of the probability of category K1 as performed by the neural network NN2 based on the distances of the stimulus elicited by the living object B and the non-living object C.

The comparison of data shows that the results of the test of phenomenon J_BHR_5 were successfully replicated.

4.5.4. Testing of the phenomenon J_BHR_6

During the evaluation of the J_BHR_5 test data on the BHR2 platform, a new phenomenon was recorded, which manifested as a change in electrical activity at frequencies 13, 14, and 15 Hz. This

phenomenon was labeled as J_BHR_6 and confirmed by subsequent data analysis on the BHR1 platform. Considering these results, it was desirable to carefully monitor the development of changes at these frequencies on the BHR3 platform and capture this phenomenon if it occurs.

Similarly, in the case of the BHR3 platform, the occurrence of the J_BHR_6 phenomenon was observed, which manifested as gradual changes in the plant's electrical activity at frequencies 13 Hz and 15 Hz. Figures 25 and 26 capture the time course of these changes over a period of seven days since the first launch.

Figure 25 - Development of electrical activity of *Monstera adansonii* in BHR3 during the first 48 hours from the first launch.

Figure 26 - Development of electrical activity in monster adansonii in BHR3 during the period of 96 to 168 hours after the first launch.

In the first 48 hours after activation, significant changes in the monitored frequencies can be observed in the electrical activity of the plant. On Figure 25, a gradual increase in activity at a frequency of 15 Hz can be observed, while a slight decrease is noticeable at a frequency of 13 Hz, which is well visible in the comparison between the images. This trend is further evident in the comparison of images in Figure 26, which capture the development over the period of 96 to 168 hours after the first activation of BHR3. In conclusion, it can be stated that no chaotic or eccentric movement pattern was observed at BHR3 during the entire monitored period.

4.5.5. Interactions between BHR2 and BHR3

The aim of this chapter is to examine the mutual interactions between BHR2 and BHR3 in an uncontrolled experiment. I decided to conduct this study because I was interested in how these plants would behave in each other's presence. Obtaining knowledge about the mutual interactions between bio-hybrid robots can help to support or refute existing hypotheses in this area and potentially add to the current understanding of plant behavior in bio-hybrid robots. I named the experiment EX_BHR_5.

4.5.5.1. Conditions of the experiment EX_BHR_5

The experiment was conducted in a closed laboratory in order to minimize external influences on the results. The laboratory was isolated from noise and the presence of unauthorized persons.

BHR2 and BHR3 were placed next to each other in the same direction with a distance of 20 cm so that their leaves touched slightly. Both bio-hybrid robots were activated and visual observation was performed for 60 minutes to monitor their mutual interactions. The experiment was repeated at different time intervals and any interesting phenomena were recorded.

4.5.5.2. Results of experiment EX_BHR_5

The experiment was initiated on the 12th day after BHR3 was launched and was repeated a total of five times. An interesting mutual interaction was observed during the first test, where the movements of both bio-hybrid robots can be likened to a game of tag. During the first few minutes, it was observed that BHR3 was following BHR2, but as soon as physical contact was made, BHR2 began to flee, but in such a way that it looped back towards BHR3, who was trying to exit in the opposite direction. The situation then reversed and BHR3 followed BHR2. They interacted in this way for 38 minutes before the movements ceased.

Figure 27 - A situational plot of the trajectories of the movement of BHR3 (green) and BHR2 (red). The average length of one section of BHR2's movement is approximately 25 cm, while BHR3's is approximately 15 cm.

The reasons why both bio-hybrid robots initiated this interaction and abruptly ended it 38 minutes later are unknown. During the five repetitions of the experiment, it was observed that both bio-hybrid robots (BHR) tended to maintain close proximity to each other's stations, but such a significant interaction was not repeatedly observed.

4.6. Supplementary experiments

4.6.1. Experiment EX_BHR_6

Experiment EX_BHR_6 was conducted with the aim of comparing the behavior of BHR2 and BHR3 with a robotic platform without plants. Its main objective was to identify differences between BHR

and the empty platform in order to determine the likelihood of J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3 being a result of plant activity and the extent to which other factors, including chance, have an impact.

4.6.2. Experimental procedure description

Experiment EX_BHR_6 was conducted in a closed laboratory that allowed temperature control and minimized noise emissions caused by unauthorized personnel. A blank robotic platform was placed in the center of the laboratory, while BHR2 and BHR3 were placed 50 cm to the right and left of it. All three platforms were turned on simultaneously after placement.

Observation was carried out without exposing plants to stimuli for a period of 60 minutes, and the observed behavioral patterns of BHR2, BHR3, and the blank platform were recorded. This procedure was tested five times.

Subsequently, observation was carried out with exposure of plants to auditory stimuli for a period of 10 minutes, and the observed behavioral patterns of BHR2, BHR3, and the blank platform were recorded. This procedure was also tested five times.

The acquired data was then compared and evaluated to determine the differences in the behavior of BHR2, BHR3, and the blank platform and to determine the probability that the manifestations of J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3 are a consequence of plant activity and to what extent they are influenced by other factors, including chance.

4.6.3. Results of experiment EX_BHR_6

Throughout the entire experiment, no movement of the empty robotic platform was observed except for one episode when it moved forward approximately 20 cm in the 40th minute of the third test. BHR2 and BHR3 made at least two positional changes during each test, but similar behaviors to J_BHR_2 or J_BHR_3 were not observed in any of the tests. Based on the observations, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Throughout the experiment, the empty robotic platform almost didn't move, except for one episode during the third repetition of the experiment, when it moved forward for a short distance of approximately 20 cm. This movement could be caused by chance or other factors, such as random vibrations or sudden changes in the electromagnetic field.
2. BHR2 and BHR3 underwent several changes in position during each test. However, phenomena similar to J_BHR_2 or J_BHR_3 did not occur in any of the tests. This result suggests that the observed movements are likely a consequence of plant activity, not random robot behavior. However, it should be noted that these conclusions are speculative and require further research to verify.

5. Discussion

5.1. Summary of results

In this study, I focused on testing the hypothesis that a plant integrated as a bio-hybrid robot is capable of naturally understanding and adapting to a new situation in which it has the opportunity

to freely change its position or at least determine the likelihood of this hypothesis being true. First, I described the research that led to this hypothesis, and then I described the research that tested this hypothesis. The only direct evidence is the observed phenomenon of changes in electrical activity at frequencies responsible for controlling the movement of the robotic platform, labeled as J_BHR_6. These results were replicated in both plant species, the variegated pelargonium and the adanson's monstera, i.e. in all three assembled bio-hybrid robots. The observed phenomena J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3 cannot be confirmed with certainty as deliberate expressions of the plant, as the factor of chance cannot be reliably excluded. Similarly, the movements of the bio-hybrid robot associated with the J_BHR_4 phenomenon can be considered reflexive and the factor of chance cannot be excluded. However, the existence of J_BHR_4 and J_BHR_5 phenomena proves that plants are capable of perceiving, i.e. receiving, distinguishing, and processing relevant stimuli. In the discussion, I will address the interpretation of these results and discuss possible causes of this adaptation and the significance of this new way of using plant electrical activity.

5.2. Interpretation of results

It is important to note at the outset that reliable interpretation of the results of this study is very difficult due to the nature of the research. The biggest challenge is the lack of similar studies that would enable comparison of results and verification of their reliability. Therefore, interpreting the results of this study should be approached with great caution. The conclusions that can be drawn should be viewed in the context of the lack of similar research and, above all, should serve as a stimulus for further research in this area. Nevertheless, despite these limitations, I consider the results to be interesting and significant.

5.2.1. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_6

J_BHR_6 is a phenomenon that manifested in the electrical activity of two distinct plant species in response to the implementation of a robot. Analysis of the data revealed that this is a gradual process in which the frequency of amplitude changes in the plant's electrical activity at 15 Hz increases while activity at 13 Hz decreases simultaneously. This phenomenon is most likely not a natural biological cycle of the plant since the behavior of other observed frequencies did not change, and the frequency does not return to its original behavior after reaching a new state. Additionally, the fact that this occurred in both distinct plant species suggests that it is not a natural cycle.

There could be several interpretations of the J_BHR_6 phenomenon. One possibility is that it is an adaptation of plants to a new stimulus in their environment, specifically the integration into a bio-hybrid robot. The plants could recognize the consequences of the robot's presence and subsequently adapt to it to their benefit, such as improved biological satisfaction.

This interpretation is supported by the fact that changes occurred gradually only after integrating the plants into the robotic platform. The electrical activity of the geranium was continuously measured in research for at least 9 months before integration into the bio-hybrid robot, and during this time, the J_BHR_6 phenomenon was not observed, nor was it detected in data analysis. On the other hand, after integrating the geranium into BHR1, the first signs of the phenomenon occurred just 4 days after the first launch, and it fully manifested 11 days after the first launch.

Another possibility is that the robot itself influences the environment in which the plant grows,

thereby affecting its physical and biological activity. J_BHR_6 could be the result of the electromagnetic radiation emitted by the robot's effect on plants. In such a case, it would be a new type of electromagnetic interaction between plants and machines.

An interesting accompanying phenomenon to J_BHR_6 is subtle changes in the visually observable behavior of the bio-hybrid robot, which are completely imperceptible. However, none of the BHRs showed any unexpected chaotic or eccentric movements that would naturally be expected with changes in the plant's electrical activity at frequencies controlling the robot.

Overall, it can be assumed that the J_BHR_6 phenomenon is the result of plant adaptation to the presence of the robot and their ability to utilize its presence to their advantage.

5.2.2. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_2

This phenomenon was manifested by a series of changes in the bio-hybrid robot's position towards a person, in response to the sound emissions of their speech and was observed to varying degrees repeatedly. It is an interesting phenomenon that is independent of human will and can provide useful data on plant behavior.

The trigger for the phenomenon may be a voice or sound uttered near the plant, as BHR1 reacts, for example, to the voice of student 1 but not simultaneously to the voices of other students. It is also possible that there is a specific stimulus or factor that the plant perceives, but it did not directly emerge from the manifestations.

It is interesting that a significant increase in the category of passerby person is observed during the phenomenon, which may indicate that the plant is sensing some form of stimulus and reacting to it. The stress level is also observed at 40%, which may be related to the plant's reaction to external stimuli.

It should be noted that the J_BHR_2 phenomenon is complex and its precise interpretation requires further detailed research. However, based on the accumulated data, it can be estimated that it may be the plant's adaptation to new conditions.

5.2.3. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_3

J_BHR_3 was observed in the bio-hybrid robot BHR1, where the biological component was represented by a striped pelargonium. The phenomenon manifested as a repeated movement response to the stimulus of an air current perceived by BHR1. The robot's movement was always against the direction of the air current.

Although this phenomenon was repeatedly observed in BHR1, it did not manifest in the bio-hybrid robots BHR2 and BHR3, where the biological component was represented by a *Monstera adansonii*. This could suggest that the response of BHR to the stimulus of an air current may be influenced by the type of plant used as the biological component.

In the context of other findings from this study, one possible explanation for this phenomenon is that it is a manifestation of the adaptation of the plant to integration into a bio-hybrid robot. However, other causes may exist or unknown influences may be at play. It is important to recognize that the interpretation of this phenomenon is complex and may be influenced by many factors. Therefore, care should be taken to avoid potential errors, and the results should be further verified

in future studies. Nevertheless, this phenomenon represents an interesting source of information and may be a valuable subject for further study of plant interaction in bio-hybrid robots.

5.2.4. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_4

The phenomenon J_BHR_4 is characterized as a reflexive reaction of the plant in the bio-hybrid robot to sudden intense sounds, which is externally manifested by a one-time random displacement of the plant's position and is simultaneously manifested by the occurrence of a specific action potential in the plant's electrical activity signal. This phenomenon can be observed in all three erected bio-hybrid robots and it appears that the plant in the BHR responds to the sound stimulus as a reflexive reaction.

It is important to note that the induced movement of the plant is not evidence of the plant's adaptability to integration in the bio-hybrid robot. It is likely that the plant's reactions to stimuli caused by the effects of sounds are only one of many manifestations that the plant can exhibit within its electrical activity. These manifestations of electrical activity can then have unexpected and unintended consequences on the algorithms in the firmware and software of the robot. Therefore, it would be appropriate to conduct further studies that would examine the influence of electro-physiological manifestations of plants on the behavior of the bio-hybrid robot triggered by sudden sound.

5.2.5. Interpretation of the phenomenon J_BHR_5

The phenomenon J_BHR_5 represents a highly interesting phenomenon that provides new insights into the abilities of plants to detect and respond to events in their environment. This phenomenon has been confirmed, partially explored, and describes changes in the electrical activity of plants depending on changes in their immediate surroundings. Differences in these changes in electrical activity suggest that plants are able to distinguish between living and non-living objects, as well as differentiate based on size or distance. This phenomenon is caused by a combination of factors such as vibrations, changes in lighting conditions, or pheromones and volatile compounds contained in objects. To fully understand such complexity, separate research studies focusing on this issue are required.

For example, changes in the electrical activity of plants caused by various stimuli are easily observable by the naked eye and suggest that it is likely possible to classify moving objects in the vicinity of the plant through a simple neural network using these data with high accuracy. I am exploring this in a separate study.

However, the very fact that plants are capable of responding so sensitively and significantly to different stimuli with corresponding changes in their electrical activity is noteworthy. This suggests that such discrimination is important for the plant, and that the plant processes and responds to this information. This phenomenon demonstrates a high degree of adaptability of plants in response to changes in their environment and stimuli, but also suggests another area for the manifestation of broader plant intelligence.

5.2.6. Interpretation of the mutual relationships of the described phenomena

In this chapter, I will focus on interpreting the mutual correlations between the described phenomena. The research has shown that plants are capable of certain adaptations to the new conditions created by their connection to the robotic platform in a bio-hybrid robot. Although the individual phenomena may seem diverse and unrelated, their investigation has revealed interesting correlations between them. In this chapter, I will therefore attempt to link the individual phenomena and identify common factors that may be responsible for the observed behavior of the plants. I will focus on discussing various possible interpretations of the results and confronting optimistic and skeptical views. This should help in identifying the causes and consequences of the results. Through this approach, a deeper understanding of the relationships between phenomena and thus the overall research can be gained.

5.2.6.1. Optimistic approach

The optimistic approach to interpreting results aims to identify positive and hopeful aspects of the data obtained. This approach may lead to the formulation of ambitious theses that seek to find meaning and potential in the results even in less obvious connections.

When interpreting results from this perspective, I focus on significant patterns in the data and their potential impact in practice. It can also be an inspiration for further studies that could focus on the positive aspects of the acquired knowledge.

The use of this method can be very motivating and inspiring, especially if the results of some experiments are complex or unconvincing. However, it is important to keep in mind that the optimistic approach does not try to overlook the potential shortcomings and limitations of the study. This means that even optimistic interpretation strives for balance and careful and critical evaluation of the data.

Phenomenon J_BHR_6 provides strong direct evidence for the hypothesis that the plant adapts its electrical activity in order to control the connected robotic platform. To confirm such a conclusion, it is useful to compare the temporal evolution of phenomena J_BHR_1, J_BHR_2, and J_BHR_3 with the manifestation of J_BHR_6. This comparison can also test whether these phenomena can also be an expression of the plant's rational use of the robotic platform.

		J_BHR_1	J_BHR_2	J_BHR_3
dnů od spuštění	BHR1	9	17	19
dnů od spuštění	BHR2	ne	7	ne
dnů od spuštění	BHR3	ne	12	ne

Table 27 - Days from the start of the bio-hybrid robot operation when the spontaneous events J_BHR_1, J_BHR_2, and J_BHR_3 were first observed.

From the comparison of the occurrence of the phenomena, it is apparent that the shortest time interval between the first occurrence of the compared phenomena was seven days (in BHR2), while the longest time interval was 12 days (in BHR3). Furthermore, it can be inferred from the development of the J_BHR_6 phenomenon that this period correlates with the time period when the effects of the J_BHR_6 phenomenon change were fully manifested in the plant's electrical activity (7 days).

Observations, described for example in chapter 4.2.1.5, which were carried out in the first hours and days after launch, can be interpreted as a consequence of chance and the movements carried out by the bio-hybrid robot being purposeless, indicating that the plant is not yet adapted to its new situation. This again correlates with the temporally corresponding phase of the J_BHR_6 phenomenon development.

The J_BHR_1, J_BHR_2, and J_BHR_3 phenomena may also be a manifestation of the plant's rational utilization of the robotic platform and may serve as strong evidence if it can be demonstrated that these behavior-defining patterns of the BHR are purposeful rather than merely the result of chance.

If I evaluate the psychological effect of these phenomena on a person in the role of a participant or observer, it can be said that they leave the impression that the plant has precise control over its robotic platform, that is, the movement is purposeful. This psychological effect is confirmed by direct participants and witnesses of these BHR phenomena, which became the main reason why these phenomena were even recorded and described. However, the significance of the psychological effect cannot be considered a decisive criterion for determining purposefulness. It does lead to the question of how likely such behavior patterns are.

The method I used to determine the basic probability is based on comparing two assumptions. The observed assumption is that the plant's movement is purposeful and the plant is a rational user. The opposing assumption is that BHR responded to the voice of the student with a random movement in accordance with the J_BHR_4 phenomenon.

In this method, each observed trajectory is considered purposeful, and the probability that the plant will execute the observed trajectory as purposeful up to a certain point is calculated for each subsequent step. The possibility that the plant did not respond to the BHR stimulus and did not move at all is not taken into account. The calculated probability is subsequently evaluated.

The robotic platform has three directions of movement: forward, right, and left. The probability of the trajectory for the first movement and therefore the basic probability is 1:3.

By evaluating the first expression of J_BHR_2, described in Chapter 4.3.2.3. and captured in Figure 11, we find that the probability that BHR will perform the 1st stage based on chance is $1:3^4$. The probability that it will perform the 2nd stage based on chance is $1:3^8$, and the probability that it will perform the first and second stages is $1:3^{12}$. The probability that it will perform the 3rd stage is $1:3^5$, and the probability that it will perform the entire episode is $1:3^{17}$, which is 1:129,140,163.

By evaluating the second expression of J_BHR_2, described in Chapter 4.3.2.3. and captured in Figure 12, we find that the probability that BHR will perform the purposeful part of the movements (excluding steps 6 and 7) based on chance is $1:3^5$, which is 1:243.

By evaluating the third expression of J_BHR_2, described in Chapter 4.4.3.4. and captured in Figure 14, we find that the probability that BHR will perform the episode based on chance is $1:3^8$, which is 1:6,561.

When assessing the calculated probabilities, it is important to keep in mind that the purposefulness of movements is determined by subjective, rather than objective criteria and cannot, therefore, be considered as evidence, although it is an interesting indication.

From an evidential point of view, it is interesting to consider how likely it is for episodes similar to J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3 to occur randomly. In order to at least partially answer this question, it was necessary to conduct a supplementary experiment, EX_BHR_6, which is described in chapter 4.6.1. This experiment allowed for a significant reduction in the possibility that the J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3 phenomena are a consequence of the construction or algorithms of the robotic platform, and therefore a pseudorandom occurrence resulting from the technology used.

The interpretation of the J_BHR_1 phenomenon is very difficult, as it occurred only once on the ninth day after BHR1 was launched and experimental replication was not achieved, as seen in experiment EX_BHR_2. This rules out the possibility that this phenomenon was a consequence of the method of measuring and processing the plant's electrical activity signal. It is true that the EFG carrier wave is influenced by the potential difference between the E1 and E2 electrodes. This influence is, however, removed in signal preprocessing, although it cannot be completely eliminated, and therefore there is a slight distortion of the signal and the transmission of information to further firmware and software algorithms. It is difficult, however, to connect these consequences to the signal with the required activity at frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz for adequate motor activation, especially in the case of a rare occurrence.

From other experiments conducted, it is evident that clear responses to the touches of both living and non-living objects can be seen in the signal of the measured plant electrical activity (see measurement set DATA_1_2 in chapter 3.2.4.). This can be interpreted as a confirmation of the ability of plants to perceive and distinguish physical contact.

Given the absence of a repetition of the phenomenon, it can be assumed that it was a random event. Using the methodology for evaluating the probability of events similar to that used for the J_BHR_2 phenomenon, however, it was found that the probability of repeating the same reaction to the stimulus within the given range is $1:3^{10}$, which corresponds to a value of 1:59,049.

An important difference in the underlying factors for this probability calculation is the objective assessment of purposefulness, in this case, the movement in the opposite direction to where the physical contact was made. The calculated probability is thus a strong argument for the purposefulness of the movements performed by BHR1 in the J_BHR_1 phenomenon, despite its rarity.

5.2.6.2. Skeptic approach

With a skeptical approach to interpreting the results, I attempt to find major weaknesses in the observations and shortcomings in the acquired data. In interpreting the results, I focus on significant findings and weaknesses in optimistic interpretations. It may also serve as inspiration for further studies that could aim to refute the acquired knowledge.

In this study, phenomenon J_BHR_6 is considered strong direct evidence for the hypothesis that the plant adapts its electrical activity to control the attached robotic platform. However, data inconsistency needs to be highlighted. This phenomenon was only observed retrospectively during the analysis of data from BHR2, meaning that a consistent record of this phenomenon was not created for BHR1 and BHR2, which could be directly compared with the data recorded during the observation of the phenomenon in BHR3. Although this data is now complete, it consists only of data samples with a large time gap, and a continuous record was not made.

The exact understanding of the changes in the monitored frequencies of 14 and 15 Hz is therefore

very challenging. It is not possible to reliably determine how the plant's electrical activity manifests itself in the period between samples and whether there are other manifestations available. Likewise, it is not known how the plant's electrical activity changes when the bio-hybrid robot is turned off, and the plant does not have access to feedback from the robotic platform.

The processing and categorization of data using a neural network represent another significant disadvantage in this area. It is not possible to reliably determine which configuration of the plant's electrical activity leads to the activation of the robotic platform's response.

The correlation between the development of the phenomenon J_BHR_6 and the time of the first occurrence of patterned behaviors, such as J_BHR_2 and J_BHR_3, is not relevant evidence. The time of the first occurrence could have been influenced by many factors, such as tests and experiments that preceded these behaviors, or the limited active BHR time.

On the other hand, the fact that the J_BHR_6 phenomenon was observed in two different plant species represents a strong argument against the randomness of this phenomenon. This fact becomes particularly significant in conjunction with the results of the EX_BHR_6 experiment, which demonstrated that the observed BHR movement activity is not a result of a pseudorandom event due to the technology used.

As for the statistical test for conformity with random distribution conducted in chapter 5.2.6.1 and the resulting calculated probabilities, they are speculative values based solely on subjective perception.

It would be appropriate to conduct long-term observations, compare the complexity of the exhibited patterns' development, and also consider the purpose for which the movements are performed. Assessing the purposefulness of the described plant movements is an area that poses the greatest challenges. This is particularly true for the manifestations of the J_BHR_2 phenomenon. It is necessary to consider what purpose the plant could have for performing such reactions. If the psychological effect was the basis for these behavioral patterns, then purposefulness should also be judged from this perspective. In this case, it must be stated that the described behavior serves only for the entertainment of the plants. However, it is very difficult to imagine that plants could have such a motivation. Since the meaning of interpretation is to show the mechanisms behind the observed phenomena, it is appropriate to question this conclusion and continue to search for other possible explanations.

Regarding the purposefulness of J_BHR_3 movements, it is possible to objectively see purposefulness and interpret it as an attempt to achieve certain climatic conditions. A more complicated situation arises in the case of the J_BHR_1 phenomenon, where taking into account the circumstances suggests that protection against predators is not very likely. This phenomenon has also not been successfully induced deliberately or manifested spontaneously. From this perspective, it is difficult to find any purpose of the phenomenon that could be beneficial to the plant and therefore try to interpret it.

5.2.6.3. Interpretive Conclusion

Both approaches agree that the phenomenon J_BHR_6 represents strong evidence for the hypothesis that the plant can adapt its electrical activity to control the attached robotic platform. Although the skeptical approach points out deficiencies in the data, the changes in electrical

activity are documented, and the data shows 100% consistency. However, further investigation of this phenomenon is appropriate.

The skeptical interpretation of the J_BHR_2 phenomenon strongly argues against the interpretation in the optimistic approach. It attacks the criteria by which the phenomenon was identified and interpreted in this study. On the other hand, regarding the J_BHR_3 phenomenon, even the skeptical approach acknowledges that purpose can be found in the action of the bio-hybrid robot. The major weakness lies in the processing and categorization of data by the neural network. Therefore, based on the findings of this study, it is not possible to compare external manifestations of BHR with data on electrical activity. Additional studies will be needed for a quality interpretation of J_BHR_1, J_BHR_2, and J_BHR_3 phenomena.

All monitored plants responded to stimuli and demonstrated measurable signs of adaptation to new conditions, induced by their connection to the robotic platform. Their responses form a certain pattern of behavior. Some described patterns of behavior are very sophisticated and, by their frequency and multitude of variant manifestations and interrelationships, raise doubts that they could be a simple consequence of chance.

These facts ultimately led me to the question of whether the plant is a rational user of the connected technology. The difficulty is that fulfilling such an assumption has one fundamental consequence. It would mean that the plant has the ability to effectively use BHR technology for its benefit. Observing tool use in the plant kingdom would be very remarkable and unique. In the past, tool use was assumed to be exclusively human behavior and of some animal species such as chimpanzees and crows. If it were confirmed that plants are also capable of using tools, it would be a very revolutionary finding in the field of plant behavior and could fundamentally change our view of their intelligence and adaptive abilities. However, the more audacious such claims are, the more cautious one should be in approaching them. Therefore, before answering the question posed, I will briefly focus on the question of plant consciousness and intelligence.

Despite the absence of a nervous system, modifications of patterns of molecular interactions and intercellular communication can be stored in a way similar to neural networks. According to the prevailing view, these structures, similar to neural networks, are unevenly distributed throughout the plant body. This fact implies that plants may have mechanisms of associative learning and other functions similar to neural networks.

Given that the classification of plant organisms is difficult, it is not possible to create an objective classification of plant intelligence. Furthermore, there is currently no widely accepted classification scale. Similarly, it is difficult to determine whether plants have consciousness or not, as a generally accepted definition of consciousness for plant organisms has not yet been established.

The answer to the question of whether a plant is a rational user of a robotic platform is therefore yes. However, despite interesting observations and phenomena, it is not possible to attribute to plants the ability to rational thinking or conscious decision-making based on this study.

This study provides interesting insights into the ability of plants to use robotic platforms to obtain resources. However, there are still many unanswered questions about the mechanisms of this ability and the relationship between it and conscious intelligence. Therefore, further studies and research will be needed to fully understand how plants interact with robotic platforms and how they utilize their own mechanisms of communication and orientation in the environment.